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D3.1 – First release of aggregated and harmonised EOVS datasets

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Glossary of terms

Item	Description
API	Application programming interface
BDI	Blue Data Infrastructure
BGC	Biogeochemical
BODC PUV	BODC Parameter Usage Vocabulary
CMEMS	Copernicus Monitoring Environment Marine Service
CMEMS In Situ TAC	Copernicus Monitoring Environment Marine Service in situ Thematic Assembly Centre
DD&AS	Data Discovery and Access Service
DIVAnd	Data-Interpolating Variational Analysis in n dimensions
EBV	Essential Biological Variable
EMODnet	European Marine Observation and Data Network
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud

EOV	Essential Ocean Variable
EWB	Eutrophication Workbench
PWB	Physics Workbench
QC	Quality Control
SA	Semantic Analyser
SDN	SeaDataNet, pan-European network for marine data management
VLab	Virtual Laboratory
VRE	Virtual Research Environment
WB	Workbench
WOD	World Ocean Database

Keywords

workbench, duplicates, quality control, EOJ, EBV

Disclaimer

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The objective of WP3 is to design, build, deploy and test analytical pipelines for generating highly qualified and harmonised data collection for some selected Essential Ocean and Biological Variables (EOV and EBV respectively). These pipelines are called 'workbenches'.

For the physical and eutrophication workbenches, these resulting data collections will integrate and harmonise different datasets from various Blue Data Infrastructures (BDIs). This includes cleaning the data collection from duplicates and applying additional quality control (QC) checks.

The EOVs considered for the physical workbench (WB1) are temperature and salinity.

The EOVs considered for the eutrophication workbench (WB2) are chlorophyll, oxygen and nutrients.

For the ecosystem workbench, EOVs and EBVs will be derived from multiple data sources and will provide interoperable and incomparable products in a user-friendly format. The EBVs considered for this workbench are plankton biomass and diversity.

In the original formulation of the project, it was planned to generate and deliver for each workbench at M20 a preliminary aggregated and harmonised dataset for essential variables. This should involve a first data homogenisation and integration, at least for some input data and over small geographical areas.

However, when the project started, there were not yet means to efficiently access the identified input datasets and to harmonise them automatically. Therefore, the priority in WP3 has been turned fully to designing a conceptual and feasible approach for the analytical workflows and formulating requirements for the system components that together will make up the workbenches. These include components for facilitating efficient and fast performing access to the different data repositories, harmonisation in syntax and semantics of output from these diverse data sources, and processing the large data collections for validation and identification and removal of duplicate data sets.

Therefore, WP3 for the Workbenches on Temperature & Salinity and Eutrophication worked closely together with WP2 and Wp5, for developing and trying out innovative technology for configuring data lakes with fast sub-setting functionality, and with WP3 partners developing new technology for semantic analysis and mapping, and for upgrading the WebODV service from Read-only to Read and Write as needed for the data processing activities. In addition, WP3 for these two workbenches has analysed and selected data repositories and formulated a common metadata profile for supporting harmonisation.

This way, WP3 has made great steps forward in formulating the analytical pipelines and architecture of the workbenches, while also providing requirements to the Blue-Cloud technical developers that are being followed up successfully.

For the ecosystem workbench, EOVs and EBVs are derived from different historical and new sources of biological plankton data through a standardised mapping and extrapolation pipeline using statistical and machine-learning approaches that aim to compensate for data scarcity and spatiotemporal biases. Very good progress has been made in developing a prototype of the novel analysis pipeline.

WP3 and the workbenches are on track.

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1. Introduction

The objective of WP3 is to design, build, deploy and test through the so-called workbenches analytical pipelines for generating highly qualified and harmonised data collections for some selected Essential Ocean and Biological Variables (EOV and EBV, respectively). These pipelines are called ‘workbenches’.

For the physical and eutrophication workbenches, these final datasets will integrate and harmonise different datasets from various Blue Data Infrastructures (BDIs): SeaDataNet, EMODnet, Copernicus Marine Service and World Ocean Database (WOD). This includes cleaning the data collection from duplicates and applying additional quality control (QC) checks.

The EOVs considered for the physical workbench (WB1) are temperature and salinity.

The EOVs considered for the eutrophication workbench (WB2) are chlorophyll, oxygen and nutrients.

For the ecosystem workbench, EOVs and EBVs are derived from different historical and new sources of biological plankton data through a standardised mapping and extrapolation pipeline using statistical and machine-learning approaches that aim to compensate for data scarcity and spatiotemporal biases. WB3 will provide interoperable and intercomparable products displayed in multiple user-friendly formats. The EBVs considered for this workbench are plankton biomass and diversity.

In an early stage, it became clear that a big effort with several technical developments would be needed to fulfil the initial plans and new strategies were considered to obtain the main objectives, which remain unchanged:

- Scientific objectives: to obtain harmonised and validated EOVs and EBVs datasets, integrating several data released from various BDIs, by the end of the project;
- Technical objectives: to develop dedicated new tools to retrieve, harmonise and integrate data from various sources taking advantage of the IT capacity offered by Blue Cloud (cloud computing platforms, data lakes, VRE, specific formats, etc.).

Deliverable will go deeper into the analyses performed and provide a conceptual and feasible solution for the analytical workflows, also formulating requirements for the system components that together will make up the workbenches. The development of these components is well underway in a cooperation of WP3 with WP2 and WP5. Finally, the Deliverable will give an outlook on the further development and implementation of the workbenches that will deliver high-quality data collections and which can be operated at regular intervals for maintaining those data collections.

2. Strategy used for the workbenches

2.1. The strategy and the different steps to build the physical and the eutrophication workbenches

To have a common overview and understanding as well as to take into account other international initiatives, the 2 workbench (WB) teams have conducted an extensive literature review through the organisation of expert lead seminars from the Blue Data Infrastructures (BDIs) identified as input sources for the WBs and have written detailed and precise reports:

- Physical WorkBench (PWB) Literature Survey (Simoncelli et al., internal report)
- [Eutrophication WorkBench \(EWB\) Literature Survey](#) (Giorgetti et al., internal report)

Considering these reports and the IT functionalities (Assante 2024; Schaap 2024) available as well as continuous exchanges with technical work package experts, the general strategy, the workflows and different implementation steps of the 2 WBs have been defined.

The realisation of the WBs is meant to speed up the marine data value chain (Figure 1) and to facilitate rapidly deriving midstream data products and downstream information products. In the present landscape, a digital ecosystem of BDIs assembles and validates marine data coming from different data providers and different platforms and would like to compare themselves to each other. Blue-Cloud 2026 aims at delivering, through the WBs, datasets and operational workflows instrumental for deepening research of the ocean, facilitating ocean state assessment (indicators and reports) and running applications (VLabs, Digital Twins of the Ocean - DTO). The midstream services developed by Blue Cloud WBs 1&2 and presented here allow semantic and scientific data integration.

Figure 1 - Marine data value chain (modified from Simoncelli et al., 2022 <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-823427-3.00001-3>).

The midstream services includes several IT dependencies : 1) the further development of the Blue-Cloud Data Discovery and Access Service (DD&AS); 2) the implementation of a Blue-Cloud Data Lake (BEACON) in the Virtual Research Environment (VRE); 3) the further development of webODV and other tools for interactive data exploration, visualisation and validation. As it is explained in detail in the following sections, the main workflow steps for WBs 1&2 to derive added value EOVS datasets from multiple Blue Data Infrastructures (BDIs) include: metadata harmonisation, data integration, duplicate removal and additional QC.

The Blue-Cloud DD&AS (Schaap 2023 and 2024), one of the core components of the technical framework, has been designed initially to facilitate the discovery and retrieval of datasets and products from BDIs and interact with the Blue-Cloud VRE (Assante 2024) for populating its datapool. The expansion and optimisation of the DD&AS service consists of the deployment of **data sub-setting and extracting services** and the implementation of Blue-Cloud **data lakes** for use by the WBs and the Virtual Laboratories (VLabs). A specific data lake configuration, which adopts the new [Beacon](#) technology, has been co-designed and is under development for the WBs to merge and harmonise a number of data collections for selected EOVS from multiple BDIs. The original vision was to build up and maintain data lakes for specific parameters by regularly extracting specific BDI data repositories and deploying them into the VRE to provide data for the WBs workflows. The demanded sub-setting capabilities will allow slicing predefined data files, querying for parameters, depth, location, time period and other criteria to create homogeneous result files that contain selected values and associated metadata. This subsetting solution will overcome one of the most

important hurdles to working in a VRE: direct access to a harmonised data subset containing only the necessary data and metadata. In fact, the ever-increasing challenge is to achieve performance when accessing and retrieving big data resources uniformly from multiple data repositories.

Beacon offers to the WBs powerful query capabilities and can filter on ranges, polygons and metadata. Multiple monolithic Beacon instances have been created from the data repositories and data collections requested by the WB1 and WB2 teams and will be soon available on the Blue-Cloud VRE to start testing data access and retrieval through specific queries.

The effort to fulfil the WBs requirement of providing homogeneous output from multiple data repositories and collections, not only for parameters and units, but also for a core set of metadata, requires **semantic mapping**. The improvement of semantic expressions across data assets, and the creation and management of semantic mappings between metadata output from several federated BDIs, is ongoing. It will ultimately enhance the DD&AS capabilities and can be capitalised upon for solving the metadata and vocabularies mapping challenge within the Beacon data lake solution. This work is done in close cooperation between MARIS, NOC-BODC, CNR, selected BDIs, WB1 and WB2 teams. The target is to create two Beacon instances for WB1 and WB2 respectively, merging and harmonising the selected datasets from some BDIs with a regular and controlled updating mechanism and making them available in the VRE.

The input datasets to be used for the WBs have been rapidly identified by the partners and largely described in the Literature Surveys. They belong to the following BDIs data repositories or data collections:

- SeaDataNet, CMEMS In Situ -CORA, EuroArgo and World Ocean Database for the physical WB;
- EMODnet-chemistry, CMEMS In Situ -BGC and WOD for the eutrophication WB.

WP2 conducted detailed analysis (Schaap 2023) on the discovery and access of the main BDI's data, data products and relative metadata information in order to enhance DD&AS service and deliver innovative, harmonised and fit-for-purpose solutions to the WBs.

A comparative preliminary analysis of the metadata information associated with each identified data source has been conducted in parallel by WB1 and WB2, focusing on the most important information (see [Eutrophication WorkBench \(EWB\) Literature Survey](#), Table 3) to be preserved in the WBs integrated datasets and for further data analytics (duplicates detection and further QC).

According to the recommendations about **harmonisation of data information** from EuroSea project ([D3.7 "Network harmonisation recommendations"](#) Obaton *et al.* 2022), a list of essential and harmonised metadata information and relative convention to be associated with the WB1 and WB2 datasets has been suggested by the WBs experts to the WP2 team and is reported in Table 1. Many elements from the core metadata profile might be supported by SeaDataNet vocabularies (suggested conventions in Table

1) promoting semantic interoperability. Additional key metadata information to be associated with each data in order to assure its full traceability and update is: the identifier of the source BDI, its unique identifier within it and the access date.

The data in this table is not yet fully updated, as it reflects the current draft version at M20 (14 August 2024). The final updates and revisions will be completed in the coming months and finalised by M42.

Key metadata	Description
source BDI	
unique identifier in the source BDI	SeaDataNet/EMODnet Chemistry Local CDI+EDMO CMEMS CORA/EuroArgo DC_REFERENCE+id WOD Accession number/ database ID
access date to source BDI	YYYY-MM-DD
platform	L06 (types), B76 (models) and C17 (instances)
instrument	L05 (types) and L22 (models)
variable	P01
variable standard name	P07 (if required) - could be derived from P01 or I-ADOPT mappings
units	P06
quality flag	L27 for identification of source flag scheme, and L20 (SeaDataNet) and/or L34 (IODE) for harmonisation
time	YYYY-MM-DD THH:MM:SSZ in 24 hours mode and UTC
geographic position	reference coordinate system WGS84
depth	
organisation (originator, holding centre)	EDMO code
project	EDMERP code
cruise	CSR
date update	

Table 1 - Suggested essential metadata information and relative convention to be associated with the Blue Cloud EOvs dataset

Once the list of essential metadata to be harmonised was defined by the WBs, work could start on identifying the values that required semantic harmonisation for each of the input datasets. Values and terms used for Parameters, Units, Platforms and Instruments, were provided by the WBs to partner NOC-BODC for further analysis. Analyses were performed manually using a number of methods that also included the use of BODC’s new **Semantic Analyser** tool (SA). A number of **correspondence tables** were built, matching the expected incoming values to values expected from the suggested conventions listed in Table 1. Some of this work is still on-going, particularly for platforms where the list of values can be very

large and the vocabulary used very heterogeneous and of variable quality. The outcome of this analysis will be used to implement mappings in the NERC Vocabulary Server whenever possible, making these mappings fully “FAIR”. Different strategies using both direct mappings and “smart” mappings, will be used in order to optimise scalability and facilitate long-term maintenance. In both cases, the mappings will be made available to Beacon via SPARQL queries to the NVS SPARQL Endpoint. For situations where semantic mapping cannot be implemented (i.e. the terms and codes used are not accessible as Uniform Resource Identifiers or URIs), the mappings between source and the standardised values will be hardcoded in Beacon using a correspondence table provided by BODC. Beacon will treat the other remaining metadata fields and their contents as secondary metadata, for which harmonisation is not necessary. However, secondary metadata can be queried if needed. The results of the semantic analysis carried out as part of this work are also being used to refine the SA and its Knowledge Base.

Detail of the semantic analysis carried out is presented in section 3.1. So far we can be confident that, for the data sources and the values defined by the WBs, we can achieve 100% harmonisation for parameters, 100% harmonisation for units when coupled with the unit conversion functionality developed as part of the [EOv-Future](#) project, and currently between 25 to 50% for instruments and platforms.

An iterative approach will be necessary to progressively improve the semantic harmonisation of instruments and platforms, working with BDIs (feedback loop) but also extending or improving existing controlled vocabularies in the SA Knowledge Base (SA-KB) and the associated automated mapping methods. This will ultimately enable us to deliver homogenised datasets for specific EOvs as requested by the scientists working on the WBs. Before that, and this is where we are, first tests can be done on the whole treatment chain. Successive enhancement shall be made via an iterative process to reach the requested scientific level.

Once the mapping rules are implemented in the NVS, Beacon (Schaap 2024) will apply them to provide output homogenised datasets from two integrated instances and bring, where possible, parameters, units, quality flags and associated core metadata from the individual data collections under a homogeneous index. This work is planned to start in September when two integrated Beacon instances will be prepared for the Physical WB and Eutrophication WB.

The homogenised datasets prepared by Beacon can then be subsetted by specific queries, exported in ODV spreadsheet format and loaded into the webODV online service on the Blue-Cloud VRE for the successive analytical steps. The webODV service will allow data exploration and visualisation, useful to first validate the outcome of Beacon dataset integration and homogenization, but also to conduct duplicates analysis and further QC. In fact, the new webODV read-and-write version includes many functionalities for analyses, plots, annotations and exports that might be used to produce the highly qualified, validated and harmonised EOvs datasets.

The scientists will analyse the homogenised datasets, performing duplicates' detection and handling and an additional QC on the data. They will implement automatic workflows, deploying specific tools on the VRE for duplicates check and for further QC, to guarantee consistency and the highest quality of the output EOvs datasets with respect to the input ones. webODV can then be used to validate the final result of the automatic pipeline. The WBs experts are also considering a workflow orchestrator for the organisation of the different steps to be followed from the input to the output datasets.

In the meantime, scientific and technical experts are preparing for deployment of the different IT tools and APIs on the Blue Cloud VRE and 2 WB Vlabs have been set up with the initial requirements (JupyterLab, RStudio, webODV) specified by the WB teams. The WB1 VLab has been created and can be accessed at <https://blue-cloud.d4science.org/group/physics-workbench>, while the WB2 VLab can be accessed through the following link <https://blue-cloud.d4science.org/group/eutrophication-workbench>. The WB1 and WB2 Vlabs have also been added to the Blue-Cloud VRE Gateway at <https://blue-cloud.d4science.org/group/Blue-Cloud-gateway>.

Indeed when the homogenised (in terms of metadata and data) files will be ready, developments and studies will be done on the VRE using several IT tools and API available on the VRE. Some of these APIs are generic, others are more specific for the WB construction as the ones that will be used to detect and remove duplicates and the ones allowing additional data QC.

The output files, one per selected EOv, will be the final deliverable.

2.2. The strategy and the different steps to build the ecosystem workbench

For the ecosystem workbench, the chosen strategy is slightly different, because biological and biodiversity data is far less homogeneous than biogeochemical and physical data. Indeed, biological data are subject to substantial bias and uncertainty in methodological accuracy, space, time, and taxonomic resolution, with the main modern sampling methodologies (optical imaging, molecular methods such as metagenomics or metabarcoding, microscopy, flow cytometry, etc.) differing substantially across all these aspects. Furthermore, data is usually not provided in units suitable for the user community (e.g., climate and marine ecosystem modellers, policy makers, any stakeholders interested in biological EOvs/EBVs), thus requiring conversion from recorded abundances, for instance, to biomasses (Buitenhuis et al. 2013), or aggregation across multiple observations (e.g. from presence-absence patterns to biodiversity; e.g. Benedetti et al. 2021, 2023).

In the current workbench, the focus is on new high quality biological EOvs and EBVs associated with plankton biodiversity and biomass. To provide these data products, work on the standardisation and annotation of (meta)data is paired with the provision of new data synthesis products into the Blue-Cloud

environment and the development of novel statistical and machine-learning pipelines that allows for the extrapolation and mapping of data in space and time.

Specifically, this workbench combined multiple important strands of work that will lead to an improvement of European biodiversity and marine biology data: (1) metadata annotation of molecular biodiversity data based on taxonomic and geographical information, thus identifying marine data (EBI-ENA), (2) the provision of standardised novel metagenomics and metabarcoding datasets processed and analysed through a consistent, state-of-the-art bioinformatics pipeline MGnify (EBI), (3) taxonomic and metadata standardisation as well as abundance-to-carbon conversion algorithms for datasets produced during previous marine plankton biomass and diversity data synthesis initiatives such as MAREDAT (Buitenhuis et al. 2013) and sister EU projects AtlantECO (AtlantECO-BASE; Vogt et al. 2023), including new data on phyto- and zooplankton diversity (ETHZ), plankton functional type abundance and biomass (ETHZ, SU), trait (transparency, SU) and community composition data (ETHZ, EBI), and (4) the development of state-of-the-art species distribution modelling pipelines designed for the extrapolation and integration of scarce and strongly biased marine data to map and extrapolate data while compensating for their spatiotemporal and taxonomic biases (Righetti et al. 2019; Benedetti et al. 2021, 2023; Knecht et al., 2023; AtlantECO-MAPS; Vogt et al. 2023b).

To this end, the project takes a **step-by-step approach**. First, quality-controlled and harmonised biological presence-absence, as well as relative and absolute abundance, biomass data are combined with environmental predictor data offline to develop a state-of-the-art species distribution modelling pipeline for scarce and biased marine data with an emphasis on a rigorous quality control of the output products and a quantitative derivation of uncertainties. In parallel, efforts are made to increase the availability and extent of new and harmonised traditional, molecular and imaging plankton datasets as inputs to the modelling pipeline within the Blue-Cloud environment. Third, a prototype of the pipeline is deployed on the Blue-Cloud infrastructure alongside the quality-controlled data sets. In a last step, the method is optimised for high performance computing, and each uploaded, pre-processed data set is successively replaced by data products directly accessed via Blue-Cloud's data lake/data access and discovery service.

Specifically, steps include (1) the use of quality-controlled data from e.g. AtlantECO-BASE (Vogt et al. 2023), PhytoBase (Righetti et al., 2019), and ZooBase (Benedetti et al. 2021) paired with standard environmental predictor data (World Ocean Atlas, SOCAT, see section 3 below), in order to develop a state-of-the-art, rigorously quality controlled species distribution modelling pipeline (Schickele et al., submitted) to produce global-scale species distribution maps that extrapolate scarce and biased observations to the global scale, and to rigorously assess and provide spatiotemporally resolved, quantitative uncertainties in the extrapolated patterns of biomass and biodiversity (see section 3.3 below). This pipeline is structured in a flexible way, so that binary (presence-absence or presence-only),

continuous (concentrations, abundances), or proportion data (relative reads) can be handled. The aim is for this pipeline to be automatised as far as possible within the Blue-Cloud environment, so that all data products can be regenerated and improved iteratively, and the approach can be extended to multiple new data types and data archives, and generalised to novel data products, as more biological data becomes available in the future.

Between M01-20 of the project, an extensive range of biological datasets were downloaded, homogenised and quality controlled on local servers, based on AtlantECO metadata standards (Vogt et al., 2023). Secondly, a prototype of the species distribution modelling pipeline was developed locally (Schickele et al., in prep.), which has been ported to the Blue-Cloud infrastructure in May 2024. In parallel, environmental predictor data have been collected, homogenised, and ported to the Blue-Cloud VRE environment. Data annotation work at ENA has also been successful in attributing a biome denomination to 10.3 of the 46 million molecular samples recorded at ENA (May 2024) based on geographic and taxonomic criteria, with 17% thereof identified as marine samples. Furthermore, work at EBI on the wide range of output products potentially contributing to the determination of EOvs and EBvs associated with biomass, species distribution and diversity has resulted in the generation of new data products, (currently being tested) including ASVs, from the next version of the MGnify metabarcoding bioinformatics pipeline ahead of its production release, expected in Q1 of 2025.

First results for plankton diversity and plankton functional type biomass have been obtained locally, and initial prototypes are also on the Blue-Cloud environment, with an optimisation of pipelines and data access ongoing in collaboration with WPs 2 and 5. If possible, the input data could potentially be visualised jointly with WB1 and WB2's output products.

3. Description of the deliverables

3.1. WB1 and WB2 - Semantic harmonisation

In a first instance, the WB teams focused on 4 key metadata elements: Platforms, Instruments, Parameters, and Units.

3.1.1. Parameters

The following types of parameters are targeted by the WB:

- Physical WB: Temperature and Salinity
- Eutrophication WB: Temperature, Salinity, Oxygen, Chlorophylls, Nutrients

with data coming from the following data sources and products:

- Physical WB: SeaDataNet, CMEMS (in situ CORA), Argo, WOD
- Eutrophication WB: SeaDataNet, EMODnet chemistry, CMEMS (in situ BGC), WOD

With this information, a list of source parameters per data source was compiled by partner NOC-BODC, identifying the vocabularies used in each one (Table 2).

Data source BDI product	Parameter Vocabulary used
SeaDataNet	SeaDataNet Parameter Discovery Vocabulary (P02) and BODC Parameter Usage Vocabulary (P01)
CMEMS (T&S CORA)	MEDATLAS Parameter Usage Vocabulary (P09)
Argo	Argo parameter codes (R03)
WOD	WOD codelist
EMODnet chemistry products	EMODnet Chemistry aggregated parameter names (P35)
CMEMS (BGC)	MEDATLAS Parameter Usage Vocabulary (P09)

Table 2 – Vocabulary resources used to identify parameters in the data products required by the Physical and Eutrophication Work Benches.

Two approaches to semantic harmonisation were then considered:

1- Match similar concepts from these different semantic resources to one common identical or broader concept like e.g. those contained in the P35 or A05 collections as initially suggested in the deliverable D2.3 [D2.3 - FAIR-EASE semantic brokerage service](#), prepared by the FAIR-EASE team, a project cooperate with (and potentially lose information); or

2- Retain as much information as possible by mapping incoming concepts to a common controlled vocabulary that can accommodate both broad and narrow definitions of variables.

For example, one may have:

- A SeaDataNet dataset with the P01 parameter label and identifier: “Concentration of chlorophyll-a {chl-a CAS 479-61-8} per unit volume of the water body [particulate >GF/F phase] by filtration, methanol extraction and fluorometry” (<http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P01/current/CPHLFMP1/>)
- An EMODnet chemistry data product with the P35 label and identifier: “Water body chlorophyll-a” (<http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P35/current/EPC00105/>)
- A CMEMS dataset with the parameter label and identifier: “CHLOROPHYLL-A TOTAL” (<http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P09/current/CPHL/>)
- The WOD dataset with the WOD code 11 which stands for “Total Chlorophyll [Chl] unless specified”

If one wanted to harmonise these 4 sources to one common parameter label and code then one would need to select a term that is broad enough to encompass all of them. Since the least precise term in the example above is the WOD term (“Total Chlorophyll [Chl] unless specified”) then one would need to group all the other variables under a label that matches that broad term - hence chlorophyll concentration and not chlorophyll-a concentration.

The other approach is to use a parameter labelling vocabulary that codes the information that is coming in without dumbing down. The BODC Parameter Usage Vocabulary (P01) is such a vocabulary because it provides URIs for parameter labels that range from very broad with the minimum possible information to very specific with information about key elements of measurement protocol.

Taking the example provided above, Table 3 shows that every one of these parameters can be expressed using an existing P01 concept without loss or distortion of meaning.

Data source	Source label	Source code	BODC P01 label	BODCP01 URI
WOD	Total Chlorophyll [Chl] unless specified	11	Concentration of chlorophyll {Chl CAS 1406-65-1} per unit volume of the water body	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P01/current/CHLTVOLU/
CMEMS	CHLOROPHYLL-A TOTAL	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P09/current/CPHL/	Concentration of chlorophyll-a {chl-a CAS 479-61-8} per unit volume of the water body [particulate >unknown phase]	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P01/current/CPHLZZXX/
EMODnet chemistry products	Water body chlorophyll-a	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P35/current/EPC00105/	Concentration of chlorophyll-a {chl-a CAS 479-61-8} per unit volume of the water body [particulate >unknown phase]	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P01/current/CPHLZZXX/

Table 3 – Example of a correspondence between different types of incoming parameters concepts for chlorophyll/chlorophyll-a products and their matching concept from the BODC PUV.

Discussion with the WBs and in particular with the WB2, emphasised that it was important to keep as much detail as possible available to the researcher for as long as possible within the VRE environment enabling users to select and deselect, include in an aggregation and remove from an aggregation at will. This confirmed that Approach #2 will be the most efficient, flexible, and future-proof approach to take.

Moreover, the BODC PUV is an I-ADOPT-compliant parameter vocabulary. This means it is possible to express its concepts according to the I-ADOPT framework. For example, each of the terms described above can be linked to their property, object of interest and matrix as follows:

<https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P01/current/CPHLZZXX/>

hasProperty “Concentration per unit volume”

hasObjectOfInterest “chlorophyll-a”

hasMatrix “water body”

<https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P01/current/CHLTVOLU/>

hasProperty “Concentration per unit volume”

hasObjectOfInterest “[chlorophyll](#)”

hasMatrix “water body”

The atomic components are selected from NVS collections or from trusted external semantic resources that comply with linked data and W3C standards, and are accessible via SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language. This means that additional curated information can be used to enrich queries.

For example:

“chlorophyll” in the NVS (<http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/S27/current/CS003268/>) is mapped with a sameAs relationship to “chlorophyll” in ChEBI (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/chebi/searchId.do?chebiId=CHEBI:28966>) giving access to the additional information contained within the chemistry-focused ChEBI knowledge base.

The full list of expected variables and their mapping is provided as an Appendix.

3.1.2. Units

Units provided alongside the data will be harmonised using the BODC Units Vocabulary (P06). This will enable to capitalise on the pioneering work on unit conversion done as part of the EOSC-Future Dashboard of the Environment (Vermeulen et al 2023). Table 4 lists the expected units and their mappings to P06 concepts. It also provides the link to the mapping established in the NVS between BODC P06 and matching unit concepts in the QUDT ontology (<https://www.qudt.org/>). This link will be used by a SPARQL query to power unit conversion in Beacon.

Incoming Units	P06 label	P06 URI	Mapping to QUDT
Decibars	Decibars	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P06/current/UPDB	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/mapping/E/391252/
Degrees Celsius	Degrees Celsius	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P06/current/UPAA	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/mapping/E/391280/
Metres	Metres	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P06/current/ULAA	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/mapping/E/391413/
Micrograms per litre	Micrograms per litre	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P06/current/UGPL	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/mapping/E/391525/
Micromoles per kilogram	Micromoles per kilogram	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P06/current/KGUM	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/mapping/E/396075/
Micromoles per litre	Micromoles per litre	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P06/current/UPOX	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/mapping/E/396999/
Milligrams per cubic metre	Milligrams per cubic metre	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P06/current/UMMC	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/mapping/E/392043/
Parts per thousand	Parts per thousand	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P06/current/UPPT	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/mapping/E/391119/
Percent	Percent	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P06/current/UPCT	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/mapping/E/391686/
Dimensionless	Dimensionless	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P06/current/UUUU	Not applicable

Table 4 – Units of measures associated with WB-targeted parameters and their mapping to P06

3.1.3. Platforms

Observation platforms (ships, satellites, gliders, drones, etc) can be identified at the instance level by a name, a call sign, a unique identifier. Platforms may also be identified at a platform type or model level. Platform types are useful to regroup platform instances into well-defined categories that users can select from, e.g. filter results on a particular type or types of platform, and exclude others. The ability to identify and select platform models may be useful for gliders and argo floats.

Platform types

Platform types can be harmonised against the SeaVoX Platform Categories Vocabulary (<https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L06/current/>), a 2-level hierarchy of grouping terms used for vehicles, structures or organisms capable of bearing instruments or tools for the collection of physical, chemical, geological or biological samples or data (Table 5).

Incoming platform type labels	Source	L06 label	L06 URI	Alternative URIs
“Argo”	WOD	drifting subsurface profiling float	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L06/current/46/	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/B76/current/B760006/ could also be used
“Glider”	WOD	surface glider or sub-surface glider	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L06/current/3C/ http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L06/current/27/	Matching incoming data to either of these L06 might not be possible. If so we will need to consider either creation of a unique B76 “Unspecified ocean glider” as suggested above for Argo floats or propose the creation of a generic “ocean glider” term in L06.
“Naval vessel”	WOD	naval vessel	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L06/current/39/	N/A
“Offshore structure”	WOD	offshore structure	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L06/current/16/	N/A
“Research vessel”	WOD	research vessel	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L06/current/31/	N/A
“Small boat”	WOD	man-powered small boat or self-propelled small boat	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L06/current/3A/ http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L06/current/33/	A unique broader L06 concept could be used for all “small boats”: http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L06/current/3Z/

Table 5 – Examples of content mapping related to observation platforms from the CORA and WOD data sources.

Note that, in the L06 collection, the existing matching term for “glider” (<http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L06/current/6A/>) applies to an airborne platform and should not be used for the autonomous platforms operating in the marine environment. Instead a distinction is made between either gliders operating on the sea surface (<http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L06/current/3C/>) or in the sub-surface (<http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L06/current/27/>).

Platform instance

Identification at the platform instance level plays a key role in assisting with duplicate check algorithms. In order to be able to do that it is needed to: a) agree on a common vocabulary to uniquely identify platform instances, and b) match incoming source labels to their respective unique identifiers.

The physical WB supplied NOC-BODC with a list of platform identifiers used in the CORA (<https://data.d4science.net/TDb9>) and WOD (<https://data.d4science.net/6Z5c>) products. These were extracted from the Mediterranean Sea ODV collections, accessed from the relative BDIs and imported into ODV. The list of platforms has been extracted thanks to a specific ODV functionality which gathers all unique values for a selected metadata within a data collection. These platform-identifying labels and codes were assessed by NOC-BODC using:

1. the Semantic Analyser (SA) (using the upload text file option) with and without deprecated terms included;
2. targeted custom queries against information held in the BODC NVS database.

The WB advised that Argo platform information would be sourced directly from EuroArgo and therefore any Argo platform information coming from either CORA or WOD could be ignored.

Preliminary findings for the WOD list, using the latest version of the SA, were as follows:

- 42% of the WOD platform list (461 out of a total of 1089) had exact matches with the preferred labels of ICES platform codes from the C17 NVS collection;
- However, for 43% of those exact matches (N=197), the C17 concepts were deprecated concepts;
- Investigation will be carried out to clarify the reason for deprecation but known reasons include either the fact that the entity described was not a platform instance but a platform category (e.g. “AIRCRAFT”, “AIRPLANE”, “NAVY SHIP”), or it was not a valid entry (e.g. “MULTIPLE SHIPS”), or it was duplicating an existing entry (often caused by spelling variations);
- The name itself is insufficient as many have more than one potential match due to the fact that many ships share the same name;
- The IMO and call sign identifiers do not always return unique C17 records neither;

- The SA returned some valid proximity and wild-card matches that will need to be investigated if no other matching method yields results. Proximity and wild-card matches include differences in the structure of the label, misspellings, differences in translation from a different alphabet (e.g. Cyrillic) into the Latin alphabet.

It was noted that the WOD platform names include the “call sign” and this could be compared with information held in the description field of the ship codes held in the NVS C17 collection in a secondary targeted matching search. This work is on-going and will be prioritised according to WB needs. In the meantime, there are enough exact matches to enable testing to take place.

The CORA file consisted of a list of different kinds of unlabelled identifiers with no additional information and some broad terms like e.g. “SHIP” which had the most records associated with it but is not identifying a platform instance. Instead, the term would only match a very broad platform category in L06 (i.e. <http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L06/current/30/>). Visual check allowed to identify different types of known identifiers; however, as for the WOD, the matching has been time consuming and the use of unique URIs to identify platform instances would facilitate interoperability in the future.

Table 6 shows a summary of analysis results.

Data source	Number of entries	Match on IMO	Match on call sign	Match on WMO number	Match on C17 preferred labels	Number of matches to deprecated C17 concepts
WOD	1090	123	317	31	461	197
CORA	1737	tdb	tdb	tdb	tdb	tdb

Table 6 – Summary of high level content analysis of the observation platform list from the CORA and WOD data sources.

This work is on-going and will be prioritised according to WB needs.

3.1.4. Instruments

Instrument identification (sensors and sampling collectors) is a key element of information that can help the user decide on the data fitness-for-purpose and limitations, but also to eventually assign Type B uncertainties to the measurements (Cowley et al. 2021).

The physical WB provided lists of sensor and instrument information extracted from the [CORA](#) and [WOD](#) data products in 3 separate lists: WMO_INSTRUMENT_TYPE, WMO_INSTR and WOD Instrument - Table 7.

Data source	Number of entries	Subset analysed	Preliminary analysis summary and comments
WMO_INSTRUMENT_TYPE (CORA)	37	37	74% exact matches with WMO_INST list
WMO_INST	57	57	L33 will be to be used for XBTs to complement L22 so that fall rate equations are also taken into account
WOD_v5	273	273	6 proximity matches with L22 and 453 wildcard matches which will require further analysis

Table 7 – Summary of content related to sensors and instruments coming from the CORA and WOD data sources.

The CORA list contained 37 codes. In a first instance, the codes contained in the list were analysed against WMO Code Table 1770. WMO "Common Code Tables C-3 (CCT C-3): Instrument make and type for water temperature profile measurement with fall rate equation coefficients. Note that Argo platforms are included in this analysis because the analysis was done before NOC-BODC was made aware that Argo metadata would be fetched from EuroArgo sources and not from CORA or WOD. For the record, the following sources were used as references:

- WMO Codes Manual (official): <https://library.wmo.int/>
- WMO GitHub: <https://github.com/wmo-im/CCT/blob/master/C03.csv>
- WMO GitHub ([merge branch](#))
- NODC NOAA website: [Code Table 1770](#)
- L33 (last update: 2014): <https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L33/current/>
- R08 (Argo subset): <https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L33/current/>

Figure 2 illustrates results of matching CORA with the WMO codelist highlighting ambiguity for 26% of the records.

Figure 2 – CORA-WMO codes correspondence graph.

In a second step, CORA WMO codes were also compared with concepts from the NVS L22 collection using the SA. However, these only return a small proportion of exact matches (5 out of 37 analysed). Indeed, 12 out of 37 codes were XBT codes that contained not only the XBT model name but also its coefficients (e.g. “Sippican T-4 | 6.472 | -2.16”). For this reason, one L22 sensor model concept could correspond to more than one WMO codes (e.g. WMO “Sippican T-4 | 6.472 | -2.16” and “Sippican T-4 | 6.691 | -2.25” would both match to <http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L22/current/TOOL0435/>). It was therefore decided to take the XBT codes coming from CORA to a third step and compare them with content from the NVS L33 collection, a collection that was set up by SeaDataNet to extend the WMO codes for XBT sensors with machine-accessible correction coefficients.

The WOD v_5 instrument list ([World Ocean Database Code Tables \(noaa.gov\)](http://www.nodc.noaa.gov/WorldOceanDatabaseCodeTables)) was also analysed using the SA with some good near match results (Figure 3). Further analysis is needed but there is confidence that some good mappings can be obtained with the L22 and L05 vocabularies.

Analysers Method: **terms analysis**

▼ Keywords (459 Items)

▼ Proximity Match (6 Items)

▼ SeaVoX Device Catalogue(6 Items)

Search Term	Match Concept	Match Property	Status	Vocab Categories	Method
CTD: GUIDLINE 8705~10	Guidline 8705 CTD	Alternate Label	Accepted	Instrument	Text Match
CTD: GUIDLINE 8705~10	Guidline Model 8705 Digital CTD	Preferred Label	Accepted	Instrument	Text Match
XBT: DEEP BLUE (SIPPICAN)~10	Lockheed Martin Sippican Deep Blue XBT probe	Preferred Label	Accepted	Instrument	Text Match
XBT: FAST DEEP (SIPPICAN)~10	Lockheed Martin Sippican Fast Deep XBT probe	Preferred Label	Accepted	Instrument	Text Match
CTD: MEERESTECHNIK OTS-1200~10	Meerestechnik OTS-1200 CTD	Preferred Label	Accepted	Instrument	Text Match
CTD: PLESSEY 9400~10	Plessey 9400 CTD	Preferred Label	Accepted	Instrument	Text Match

▼ Wildcard Match (453 Items)

▼ SeaVoX Device Catalogue(453 Items)

Search Term	Match Concept	Match Property	Status	Vocab Categories	Method
CTD: HYDROZOND	CTD	Alternate Label	Accepted	Instrument	Text Match
CTD: ZOND-BATHOMETER	CTD	Alternate Label	Accepted	Instrument	Text Match
STD: AML STD-12 (aka AML CTD-12)	AML Oceanographic AML-6 LGR	Preferred Label	Accepted	Instrument	Text Match
STD: AML STD-12 (aka AML CTD-12)	AML Oceanographic AML-6 RT	Preferred Label	Accepted	Instrument	Text Match
CTD: AML Micro CTD (Applied Microsystems Limited)	AML Oceanographic Minos X CTD	Preferred Label	Accepted	Instrument	Text Match
STD: AML STD-12 (aka AML CTD-12)	AML Oceanographic Minos X CTD	Preferred Label	Accepted	Instrument	Text Match
CTD: CTD 90M - Multiparameter Memory Probe (Sea and Sun Technology GmbH/LTD)	AML Oceanographic X Metrec multiparameter CTD	Preferred Label	Accepted	Instrument	Text Match
In-Situ: Automated dissolved oxygen sensor: Aanderaa Oxygen Optode 3975	Aanderaa 3975 oxygen optode	Preferred	Accepted	Instrument	Text

Figure 3 – Output of text analysis of the WOD instrument list using the Semantic Analyser

This work is on-going and will be prioritised according to WB needs.

3.2. WB3 - ecosystem EOvs and EBVs

3.2.1. Target output variables

As approach, not only output/target variables are harmonised, but also rely on standardised biological input data produced in previous projects or newly generated by the project partners, as well as standardised, gridded, climatological products of a range of environmental predictor data sets. At a later point in time, WB1 and WB2 output fields could potentially serve as inputs to the mapping and extrapolation pipeline.

(a) Data types

The following types of variables are targeted by workbench 3 as output products:

- Plankton species richness (biodiversity)
- plankton (functional type) biomass

Since biodiversity is a derived property, intermediary products that are required for the computation of species richness or other diversity metrics include to date (subject to change as range of variables processed in analysis pipelines expands):

- Plankton habitat suitability index (scale from 0 to 1)
- Plankton presence-absence (binary: 0 or 1)
- Relative reads (percent)

(b) Spatiotemporal resolution

The spatiotemporal resolution of the output products is currently limited by data availability and the spatiotemporal resolution of the environmental predictor data sets used to map and extrapolate scarce and biased biological data to the global scale. At present, the maximum resolution of the possible output, computed as the maximal resolution of data provided across all necessary environmental predictors, is restricted to a 1 degree by 1 degree monthly climatology at the global scale.

Spatial resolution : 1 degree (-90 to 90°N, -180 to 180°E)

Temporal resolution : monthly (12 months; monthly climatologies)

(c) Associated metadata

All types of biological output data follow the EMODnet and CF conventions (see below).

Global attributes of the NetCDF files :

title: The title of the dataset.

summary: A brief summary or abstract describing the dataset.

Conventions: The conventions followed by the dataset, e.g., "CF-1.8".

comment: Additional comments or notes regarding the dataset, including full authorship information.

acknowledgment: Acknowledgments related to the dataset, such as funding sources and project details.

license: The license under which the dataset is released, e.g., "Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0)".

standard_name_vocabulary: The vocabulary used for standard names, e.g., "CF Standard Name Table v1.8".

data_created: The date when the dataset was created.

creator_name: The name of the dataset creator.

creator_email: The email address of the dataset creator.

institution: The institution affiliated with the dataset creator, e.g., "ETHZ".

project: The project under which the dataset was created, e.g., "Blue-Cloud2026".

naming_authority: The naming authority for the dataset, e.g., "emodnet-biology.eu".

publisher_name: The name of the publisher or the entity responsible for publishing the dataset, e.g., "Blue-Cloud2026".

publisher_url: The URL of the publisher or the project website, e.g., "<https://blue-cloud.d4science.org>".

geospatial_lat_min: The minimum latitude covered by the dataset.

geospatial_lat_max: The maximum latitude covered by the dataset.

geospatial_lon_min: The minimum longitude covered by the dataset.

geospatial_lon_max: The maximum longitude covered by the dataset.

geospatial_lon_units: The units of longitude, e.g., "degree_east".

geospatial_lat_units: The units of latitude, e.g., "degree_north".

time_coverage_start: The start time of the temporal coverage, e.g., "climatology".

time_coverage_end: The end time of the temporal coverage, e.g., "climatology".

contact: The contact information for inquiries about the dataset, including multiple email addresses if applicable.

(d) Units

Units provided alongside the data will be harmonised using Darwin Core standard notation (<https://www.tdwg.org/standards/dwc/>) for the sharing of biological information, and will be recorded in the resulting netcdf files according to CF conventions for the reporting of climate data. Table 8 lists the expected units for our target variables and their mapping to DwC and CF concepts for comparison, as well as their equivalent BODC P06 label for comparison with WB1 and WB2.

Incoming Units	BODC vocabularies (P06, others)	Darwin Code Vocabulary	CF Conventions
Location	Latitude	decimalLatitude	longitude degrees_east
Latitude	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P06/current/DEGN/	http://rs.tdwg.org/dwc/terms/decimalLatitude decimalLongitude	latitude degrees_north

Longitude (Degrees)	Longitude http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P06/current/DEGE/	http://rs.tdwg.org/dwc/terms/decimalLongitude	
Location (Depth in Metres)	Metres http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P06/current/ULAA	verbatimDepth http://rs.tdwg.org/dwc/terms/verbatimDepth	depth
Date (Year)	Years http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P06/current/UYRS	year http://rs.tdwg.org/dwc/terms/year	n/a (climatological outputs)
Date (Month)	Months http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P06/current/UMNT	month http://rs.tdwg.org/dwc/terms/month	n/a (climatological outputs)
Micromoles per cubic metre	Micromoles per cubic metre http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P06/current/CMUM	measurementValue http://rs.tdwg.org/dwc/terms/measurementValue measurementUnit http://rs.tdwg.org/dwc/terms/measurementUnit	mole_concentration_of_biological_taxon_expressed_as_carbon_in_sea_water (micromole m ⁻³)
Milligram carbon per cubic metre	Milligram per cubic metre http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P06/current/UMMC Biomass as carbon https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/S06/current/https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/S	measurementValue http://rs.tdwg.org/dwc/terms/measurementValue measurementUnit http://rs.tdwg.org/dwc/terms/measurementUnit	Mass_concentration_of_biological_taxon_expressed_as_carbon_in_sea_water (mg m ⁻³)

	06/current/SO600002		
Abundance of biological units	Abundance (quantity kind) https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/S06/current/S0600002 Value https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P06/current/UPMM/	MeasurementType http://rs.tdwg.org/dwc/terms/measurementType measurementValue http://rs.tdwg.org/dwc/terms/measurementValue measurementUnit http://rs.tdwg.org/dwc/terms/measurementUnit	Number_concentration_of_biological_taxon_in_sea_water (m-3)
Relative abundance of biological units	Proportion by number http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/S06/current/S0600070/ Value https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P06/current/UPMM/	MeasurementType http://rs.tdwg.org/dwc/terms/measurementType measurementValue http://rs.tdwg.org/dwc/terms/measurementValue measurementUnit http://rs.tdwg.org/dwc/terms/measurementUnit	Number_concentration_of_biological_taxon_in_sea_water (m-3)
Percent	Percent http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P06/current/UPCT	MeasurementType http://rs.tdwg.org/dwc/terms/measurementType measurementValue http://rs.tdwg.org/dwc/terms/measurementValue measurementUnit http://rs.tdwg.org/dwc/terms/measurementUnit	generic_percentage_measurement (%)
Dimensionless	Dimensionless http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P06/current/UUUU	MeasurementType http://rs.tdwg.org/dwc/terms/measurementType measurementValue http://rs.tdwg.org/dwc/terms/measurementValue	n/a (-)

		measurementUnit http://rs.tdwg.org/dwc/terms/measurementUnit
--	--	--

Table 8 – Quantity kinds and units of measures associated with WB-targeted parameters and their mapping to P06 and other vocabularies

(e) Output data formats

As mentioned above, data are outputted in netcdf format following Climate Forecast CF conventions (<https://cfconventions.org/>) for gridded, geoscientific data, suitable for sharing widely with an extensive range of stakeholders.. For details, please refer to: (<https://cfconventions.org/Data/cf-conventions/cf-conventions-1.11/cf-conventions.html>).

3.2.2. Biological input and environmental predictor data

(i) Biological input data - traditional microscopy observations

Data sources

Extrapolated data products are currently derived from the following data sources and products:

- AtlantECO-BASE (Vogt et al. 2023), MAREDAT (Buitenhuis et al. 2013), PhytoBase (Righetti et al. 2019), ZooBase (Benedetti et al., 2021), MGnify, Ecotaxa (Tara Oceans project, <https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/prj/377>)

All biological data and its metadata was harmonised in EU sister project AtlantECO to follow DARWIN Core standard notation (AtlantECO-BASE; Vogt et al. 2023) using World Ocean Register of Marine Species (WORMS) taxonomy for eukaryotes and NCBI reference catalogue for (meta)genomics and prokaryote data.

Vocabularies used (Table 9):

Data source product	Standard Vocabulary used
AtlantECO-BASE (Vogt et al. 2023)	DwC
MAREDAT (Buitenhuis et al. 2013)	Not fully standardised
Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF)	DwC
Open Biodiversity Information System (OBIS)	DwC

Table 9 –Vocabulary resources used to identify parameters in the input products required by the Ecosystem EOV Work Bench.

Metadata for input data

All AtlantECO-BASE input data has the following metadata structure headers, though only a subset of metadata is compulsory (taxonomic unit, longitude, latitude, depth, time of sampling)

The fields/ column headers suggested below stem from the 13 DarwinCore essential variables (template available at: <https://github.com/gbif/ipt/wiki/occurrenceData#templates> ; see also <http://rs.tdwg.org/dwc.htm>) to which we added fields we believed essential for adequately reporting, verifying and disseminating the data synthesized.

Overarching fields

1. ProjectID: Name of the overarching project (AtlantECO_H2020_GA#210591007).
2. ProjectWP: Work Package within the overarching project.
3. DataSilo: Name of data silo within WP (plastics, carbon, metaG, microscopy, imaging etc.).
4. ContactName: String with names of the people in charge of the dataset.
5. ContactAdress: String with the valid email addresses of the people in ContactName.
6. occurrenceID: AtlantECO-specific identifier to be defined (occurrenceID from the original data sources are reported in the 'Source identifying fields' and will thus be retained, when given, to ensure traceability).

Positional fields

7. decimalLatitude: Geographic Latitude in decimal degree, following the -180/+180 WGS84 Spatial Reference System (SRS).
8. decimalLongitude: Geographic Longitude in decimal degree, following the -180/+180 WGS84 SRS.
9. geodeticDatum: SRS of the spatial coordinates; give WGS84 only.
10. CoordUncertainty: Uncertainty estimate of the decimal coordinates; in metres.
11. CountryCode: ISO3166-1-alpha-2 code for the country the observations belong to.
12. eventDate: Date of the sampling event. OBIS recommends using the extended ISO 8601 format with hyphens (e.g. 'YYYY-MM-DD'). If possible, add time of the day, after the data, as follows: 'THH:MM:SS' (e.g. '2017-09-23T12:04:23').

13. eventDateInterval: Numeric values indicating the duration of the in situ sampling event (not the time spent in the lab analysing the sample).
14. eventDateIntervalUnit: Unit of eventDateInterval (e.g. seconds, minutes, hours, light-years...).
15. Year: Year of the sampling event (YYYY format).
16. Month: Month of the sampling event (MM format).
17. Day: Day of the sampling event (DD format).
18. Bathymetry: Depth of the seafloor at sampling event, in metres, ≤ 0 .
19. BathySource: String indicating whether Bathymetry was measured at sampling event or inferred a posteriori from NOAA or GEBCO based on the spatial coordinates (e.g., 'GEBCO', or 'NOAA' or 'In situ').
20. HabitatType: String indicating the type of habitat the sample was taken from (e.g. open ocean water column, river plume, river, coral reef, mangrove...)
21. LonghurstProvince: Longhurst Province the sample was taken from (one of 56 possible four-letter geocodes, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Longhurst_code).
22. Depth: Sample depth (in metres below the local sea surface); > 0 ; $= 0$ is surface.
23. DepthAccuracy: Single term that describes the accuracy of the collection depth, in metres.
24. DepthIntegral: Depth span below sea surface, in metres; > 0 ; $= 0$ if surface.
25. MinDepth: minimum depth for depth-integrated quantities, in metres, > 0 .
26. MaxDepth: maximum depth for depth-integrated quantities, in metres, > 0 .

Source identifying fields

27. ParentEventID: Describes the parent event, which is composed of one or more sub-sampling (child) events (eventID below). (e.g. AMT29, Tara Oceans st.75, CPR tow XX etc.)
28. eventID: Labels the replicate samples (or sub-samples) from a ParentEventID (e.g. a sample number from a station if multiple samples were taken at the same sampling station).
29. InstitutionCode: Custodian institution for the data record (ex: IMEV, MBA, UU, FUSP etc.).
30. SourceArchive: Describes the online archive where the data is stored (e.g. PANGAEA, OBIS, GBIF, DRYAD etc.).

31. OrigCollectionCode: Code given to the collection or the dataset within the SourceArchive (e.g. the code given to the CPR collection in OBIS/GBIF).
32. OrigCollectionID: occurrenceID given to the record/measurement in the SourceArchive. Retained to ensure traceability.
33. BiblioCitation: String indicating the bibliographic citation associated with the data.
34. BiblioCitationDOI: DOI of the bibliographic citation.
35. DateDataAccess: Date at which the data was downloaded from the SourceArchive; in the ISO 8601 format (e.g. YYYY-MM-DD).

Observation Classification fields

36. OrigScientificName: Scientific name of the plankton taxon/observation as reported in the source dataset.
37. ScientificName: Corrected scientific name of the taxon, as given in WoRMS.
38. WoRMS_ID: Uniform resource identifier issued from WoRMS for the biological taxon recorded. Not sure if the aphiaID is enough or if you require the Life Science Identifier (LSID). For instance, for *Centropages typicus* the aphiaID is 104499 and the LSID is simply 'urn:lsid:marinespecies.org:taxname:104499'. So the aphiaID seems enough (<https://www.marinespecies.org/aphia.php?p=webservice>).
39. TaxonRank: Taxonomic rank at which the taxon was identified and recorded (e.g. species, family, order...).
40. Kingdom: Either 'Animalia' (aphiaID #2), 'Plantae' (#3), 'Fungi' (#4), 'Protozoa' (#5), 'Bacteria' (#6), 'Chromista' (#7), or 'Archaea' (#8).
41. Phylum: Phylum of the taxon recorded.
42. Order: Order of the taxon recorded.
43. Class: Class of the taxon recorded.
44. Family: Family of the taxon recorded.
45. Genus: Genus of the taxon recorded.
46. Species: Species name of the taxon recorded.

47. Subspecies: Subspecies, or variety, of the taxon recorded.
48. LifeForm: The type of population organisation- and the ecological organisation of the organism recorded (e.g. "singular", "colonial", "symbiotic", "free living" etc.).
49. AssocTaxa: The function and scientific name of any taxon associated with the biological unit recorded (e.g. "HOST_Rhizosolenia").

Measurement fields (type, quantity and methodology)

50. measurementID: Identifier for the measurement or fact (information pertaining to measurements, facts, characteristics, or assertions). May be a global unique identifier or an identifier specific to the data set.
51. measurementType: The nature of the measurement, fact, characteristic, or assertion (e.g. presence, absence, length, size, abundance, concentration, microplastic counts, carbon flux rate etc.).
52. measurementTypeID: An identifier for the measurementType (global unique identifier, URI). The identifier should reference the measurementType in a vocabulary. Where possible, use an URI to identify the quantity you want to describe (e.g. S1228 for 'copies of the nifHgene', or S1230 for 'blood'). List of URIs available at BODC, see e.g.,: <http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/S12/current>.
53. measurementValue: The numeric value of the measurement, fact, characteristic, or assertion (e.g. '42' for a microscope count, or '1' for an occurrence, '0' for an absence etc.). No units.
54. measurementUnit: The unit associated with the measurementValue. Recommended best practice is to use the International System of Units (SI). Examples: m, mg, cells.m-3, mgC.m-3...
55. measurementAccuracy: Numeric value of the potential error associated with the measurementValue. Must be in the same unit.
56. measurementValueID: An identifier for facts stored in the column measurementValue (global unique identifier, URI). This identifier can reference a controlled vocabulary (e.g. for sampling instrument names, methodologies, life stages). When the measurementValue refers to a value and not to a fact, the measurementvalueID has no meaning and should remain empty.
57. Biomass_mgCm3: Biomass in unit of carbon (mgC/m3) corresponding to the measurement.
58. BiomassConvFactor: Biomass conversion factor. If too complex a conversion with multiple equations, indicate a conversion table, reference, or published data set...

59. **basisOfRecord:** Nature of the data record (e.g. 'preserved specimen', 'fossil specimen', 'living specimen' etc.).
60. **SamplingProtocol:** Indicates the sampling protocol used to make the measurement.
61. **SampleAmount:** Numeric value indicating the volume, or mass, of sample analysed to make the measurement (e.g. a volume of seawater filtered).
62. **SampleAmountUnit:** Unit corresponding to the SampleAmount (e.g. liter, ml, m3...).
63. **SampleEffort:** Indicates the time spent looking for an organism, or the area covered, the number of transect etc. So more of an indicator of sampling effort through time.
64. **DeterminedBy:** Name(s) of the people, groups or organizations who made the measurement, or identified the organism.
65. **DeterminedDate:** The date on which the measurement/identification was made (can differ from the eventDate).
66. **Note:** Any note or comment on the measurement event (e.g. 'Potential contamination', 'Heavy net clogging', 'Rough sea' etc.).

Environmental metadata fields (environmental context)

67. **Surf_temperature:** Sea surface temperature in Celsius.
68. **Temperature:** Temperature measured in Celsius at sampling event (day and depth resolved).
69. **Surf_salinity:** Same as above but for salinity.
70. **Salinity:** -
71. **Surf_nitrate_micromol:** Same as above but for Nitrates (NO₃) concentration, in micromolar (μM).
72. **Nitrate_micromol:** -
73. **Surf_phosphate_micromol:** Same as above but for Phosphates (PO₄³⁻) concentration, in micromolar (μM).
74. **Phosphate_micromol:** -
75. **Surf_Chla_mgm3:** Same as above but for Chlorophyll-a concentration, in mg.m⁻³.
76. **Chla_mgm3:**

77. Flag: Notes on quality/uncertainty of occurrence/measurement (e.g. quality-control flags, uncertainty, errors, contamination issues, taxonomic uncertainty, etc.).

NOTES

- Value for missing data (header could have been informed/ measured but was not) = 'NA'
- Value when header is just not applicable to observations = 'Not_applicable'

[\(ii\) Biological input data - Metagenomics data](#)

Information on the biogeographic distribution of marine organisms from the MGnify output product suite is currently accessible to the Blue-Cloud 2026 project and the CEPHALOPOD pipeline (Schickele et al., submitted) via the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF; www.gbif.org) as presence-only data, for those taxa with an equivalent taxonomic annotation within the World Register of Marine Species (WORMS), comprising a range of prokaryotic and eukaryotic taxa to the highest known taxonomic level, i.e. the species, family, order and/or class level, see link to all existing 23'785'374 occurrences:

MGNify

Description: MGNify is a free to use analysis platform and database of analysed microbiome sequencing projects, hosted by the European Molecular Biology Laboratory, European Bioinformatics Institute (EMBL-EBI). Microbiome research typically involves the study of all genomes present within a specific environment, such as soil, seawater or a human body site. Underpinned by dramatically falling DNA sequencing costs, metagenomic analyses have become increasingly mainstream. The approach can provide unique insights into the complex processes performed by environmental micro-organisms and their relationship to their surroundings, each other, and, in some cases, their host. MGNify offers an automated pipeline for the analysis and archiving of microbiome data to help determine the taxonomic diversity and functional/metabolic potential of environmental samples. Users of MGNify can submit their own data for analysis or freely browse all of the analysed public datasets held within the database. In addition, users can request analysis of any appropriate dataset found within the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA). To cite MGNify, please refer to the following publication: EBI Metagenomics in 2017: enriching the analysis of microbial communities, from sequence reads to assemblies. *Nucleic Acids Research* (2017) Alex L. Mitchell, Maxim Scheremetjev, Hubert Denise, Simon Potter, Aleksandra Tarkowska, Matloob Qureshi, Gustavo A. Salazar, Sebastien Pesseat, Miguel A. Boland, Fiona M. I. Hunter, Petra ten Hoopen, Blaise Alako, Clara Amid, Darren J. Wilkinson, Thomas P. Curtis, Guy Cochrane, Robert D. Finn. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkx967>

Endorsed by: [National Biodiversity Network](#)

Administrative contact: [Robert Finn](#)

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Figure 4 – Metagenomics data in MGNify (source: <https://www.gbif.org/publisher/ab733144-7043-4e88-bd4f-fca7bf858880>)

Hence, all MGNify occurrence data submitted to GBIF follow Darwin Core (Dwc) notation for biological data, and thus follows the same standardisation and metadata requirements and uses the same vocabularies as the traditional microscopy information above, see metadata headers and units, as well as Table 9 above. Marine data sources currently include occurrences from Amplicon sequencing for prokaryotes, protists, and viruses from important global microbiome expeditions such as the Tara Oceans expedition (Ibarbalz et al. 2019).

(iii) Biological input data - Imaging input data

Zooplankton transparency has been retrieved from the EcoTaxa database as discrete measurements corresponding to the stations of the Tara Oceans and Tara Polar Circle campaigns (2009-2012, Pesant et al., 2015). The samples originate from vertical net tows and were processed with a ZooScan (Gorsky et al., 2010) to obtain individual zooplankton images. The proxy variable for transparency is the species average of organism median grey level, calculated for each station from the images and expressed between 0 (completely dark) and 255 (completely clear). The DwC notation is used as listed above as headers to the data to ensure consistency with ordinary observations. Metadata include the geographic location, time of sampling, depth, data source, taxonomic lineage and measurement characteristics.

Data product	Source	Reference / Link	Resolution	File format	Variable
Zooplankton transparency	EcoTaxa	https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/prj/377	Global discrete measurements	CSV	Species-average of organism median grey (0-255)

Table 10 - Data products from marine plankton imaging as sourced through Ecotaxa

(iv) Environmental predictor data

Environmental predictor data has been downloaded in their original form, and is automatically gridded and standardised within the species distribution modelling pipeline for the mapping and extrapolation of data (Schickele et al., submitted).

The environmental predictor data was retrieved from the following resources:

Data product	Source	Reference / Link
FSLE, EKE	AVISO	https://www.aviso.altimetry.fr/en/my-aviso-plus/my-products.html
CHL, DIATO, DINO, GREEN, HAPTO, MICRO, NANO, PICO, PROCHLORO, PROKAR, POC	CMEMS	https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/OCEANCOLOUR_GLO_BGC_L4_MY_009_104/description
A_ADG, A_CHLA, M_CHLA, S_ADG, S_CHLA, S_PP, V_APH, V_PAR, A_APH, A_K490, M_K490,	GMIS	https://data.jrc.ec.europa.eu/collection/gmis

S_APH, S_K490, T_SST, V_CHLA, A_BBP, A_PAR, P_SST, S_BBP, S_PAR, V_ADG, V_K490		
co2,co3,dic,hco3,ice,omega_ar,omega_ca,ph,revelle_factor,sfco2,s_pco2,talk	OCEAN-SODA ETHZ	https://gitlab.ethz.ch/oceansoda
T, s, M, o, O, i, p, n	World Ocean Atlas (WOA)	https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/access/world-ocean-atlas-2018/

Table 11 - Summary list of sources of environmental predictor data, as used in WB3’s species distribution modelling pipeline. All variables name and processing steps are detailed below.

DESCRIPTION OF PREDICTORS FROM OBSERVATIONS

Observation-based monthly climatologies of environmental predictors were interpolated on a common grid (i.e., 1 x 1 degree resolution, global scale, gap-filled). Considered are monthly climatologies encompassing the 1900-2020 period and integrated over surface or epipelagic layers. These climatologies correspond to a set of features derived from in-situ measurements and satellite observations that are commonly used to characterise the physical (e.g., sea surface temperature), chemical (e.g., pH) and biological (e.g., chlorophyll-a concentration) conditions of water masses as well as their circulation and turbulence patterns (e.g., Eddy Kinetic Energy; EKE). All these features have been shown to have a major influence on the biology and spatial distribution of marine organisms, including plankton.

AVISO: <https://www.aviso.altimetry.fr/en/my-aviso-plus/my-products.html>

Variable: FSLE

Initial format: multimission altimetry-derived gridded backward-in-time Finite Size Lyapunov Exponents and Orientations of associated eigenvectors. These products have been computed in collaboration between CLS, LOcean, CTOH and Cnes. DOI: 10.24400/527896/a01-2022.002 gridded product, provided in delayed time and routine production of 20-day latency. As a snapshot, each map represents the sea state for a given day. One spatial resolution is available: 1/25°x1/25° on a cartesian grid.

Treatment applied: regridded to a 1 x 1 degree resolution grid, averaged into a monthly climatology (1993-2021)

Variable: EKE

Initial format: Link to raw data (needs registration):

<https://www.aviso.altimetry.fr/en/data/index.php?id=1526&L=1>

Climatological Eddy Kinetic Energy 1993 to 2021/01. Delayed Time Level-4 monthly climatology of Eddy Kinetic Energy from sea surface height above Mean Sea Surface products from multi-satellite observations over Global Ocean. From January 1993 to the last extension of the Delayed-time products, the long delayed-time dataset allows to compute statistical means of seven variables over different periods of time. Data are created from daily Ssalto/Duacs and CMEMS products. Monthly averaged corresponds to the weekly maps of delayed-time data averaging month by month from January 1993. The WB team obtains one file and one map per month since January 1993. Coverage: global (1/4°x1/4°, cartesian grid)

Treatment applied: regrided to a 1 x 1 degree resolution grid

CMEMS:

https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/OCEANCOLOUR_GLO_BGC_L4_MY_009_104/description

Variables: CHL, DIATO, DINO, GREEN, HAPTO, MICRO, NANO, PICO, PROCHLO, PROKAR

Description: Mass concentration of chlorophyll a in sea water (CHL), mass concentration of diatoms expressed as chlorophyll in sea water (DIATO), mass concentration of dinophytes expressed as chlorophyll in sea water (DINO), mass concentration of haptophytes expressed as chlorophyll in sea water (HAPTO), mass concentration of green algae and prochlorophytes expressed as chlorophyll in sea water (GREEN), mass concentration of prokaryotes expressed as chlorophyll in sea water (PROKAR), mass concentration of prochlorococcus expressed as chlorophyll in sea water (PROCHLO), mass concentration of microphytoplankton expressed as chlorophyll in sea water (MICRO), mass concentration of nanophytoplankton expressed as chlorophyll in sea water (NANO), mass concentration of picophytoplankton expressed as chlorophyll in sea water (PICO).

Initial format: 4 × 4 km, 1 Sep 1997 to 10 Jun 2024, DailyMonthly, Level 4 Gohin, F., Druon, J. N., Lampert, L. (2002). A five channel chlorophyll concentration algorithm applied to SeaWiFS data processed by SeaDAS in coastal waters. International journal of remote sensing, 23(8), 1639-1661 + Hu, C., Lee, Z., Franz, B. (2012). Chlorophyll and algorithms for oligotrophic oceans: A novel approach based on three-band reflectance difference. Journal of Geophysical Research, 117(C1). doi: 10.1029/2011jc007395 + Xi H, Losa S N, Mangin A, Garnesson P, Bretagnon M, Demaria J, Soppa M A, Hembise Fanton d Andon O, Bracher A (2021) Global chlorophyll a concentrations of phytoplankton functional types with detailed uncertainty assessment using multi-sensor ocean color and sea surface temperature satellite products, JGR, in review.

Treatment applied: regrided to a 1 x 1 degree resolution grid, averaged into a monthly climatology (1998-2020), and gap-filled (with yearly mean of the month with data at the location)

Variable: POC

Initial format: Author: Urs Hofmann Elizondo (urs.hofmann@usys.ethz.ch) I downloaded the surface POC as calculated by the GlobColour processor (<https://hermes.acri.fr>). The data products found in GlobColour

are based on the merging of the sensors SeaWiFS, MODIS, MERIS, VIIRS-SNPP&JPSS1, OLCI-S3A&S3B. The data cover 01/09/1997 to 31/01/2021 for the ocean surface at a 4km X 4km resolution. The download was done using the script "Get_GlobColourPOC.sh". Next, the individual files were merged into one, the multi-year monthly climatology was calculated, and the data were re-mapped to a 1°X1° resolution. These steps were done with the script "PrepareGlobColourPOC.py". Associated reference according to the GlobColour product user guide: Stramski. D., R.A. Reynolds, M. Babin, S. Kaczmarek, M.R. Lewis, R. Rottgers, A. Sciandra, M. Stramska, M.S. Twardowski, B.A. Franz, and H. Claustre (2008). Relationships between the surface concentration of particulate organic carbon and optical properties in the eastern South Pacific and eastern Atlantic Oceans, *Biogeosci.*, 5, 171-201. Monthly climatology of POC from monthly data between 1997 and 2020

Treatment applied: regrided to a 1 x 1 degree resolution grid, and gap-filled (with yearly min of the month with data at the location)

GMIS: <https://data.jrc.ec.europa.eu/collection/gmis>

Variables: A_ADG, A_CHLA, M_CHLA, S_ADG, S_CHLA, S_PP, V_APH, V_PAR, A_APH, A_K490, M_K490, S_APH, S_K490, T_SST, V_CHLA, A_BBP, A_PAR, P_SST, S_BBP, S_PAR, V_ADG, V_K490

Description: OCEAN COLOUR SENSORS - A_: MODIS-AQUA, T_: MODIS-TERRA, S_: SEAWIFS, M_: MERIS, P_: PATHFINDER, V_: VIIRS. DEFINITION OF DATASETS' ACRONYMS - CHLA_: Chlorophyll Concentration, K490_: Diffuse Attenuation Coefficient, PAR_: Photosynthetically Available Radiation, APH_: Absorption Coefficient of Phytoplankton at 443nm, ADG_: Absorption Coefficient of detritus/CDOM at 443nm, BBP_: Particulate Backscatter Coefficient at 443 nm, ZEU_: Surface Productive Layer, PP_: Primary Production, SST_: Sea Surface Temperature.

Initial format: The Global Marine Information System has been developed to provide the Users community with an appropriate set of bio-physical information, of importance to conduct water quality assessment and resource monitoring in the coastal and marine waters. The bulk of environmental analysis in GMIS relies on Earth Observation data, and the provision of continuous, detailed and accurate information on relevant marine biophysical parameters as derived from optical, and infrared satellite sensors. The datasets are at global scale and available at a spacial resolution of 9 and 4km.

Treatment applied: regrided to a 1 x 1 degree resolution grid, un-logged transformed, and gap-filled (with yearly min of the month with data at the location)

ETHZ SODA: <https://gitlab.ethz.ch/oceansoda>

Variables: co2, co3, dic, hco3, ice, omega_ar, omega_ca, ph, revelle_factor, sfcO2, spco2, talk

Description: Mole Concentration of CO2 in Sea Water, Carbonate Ion Concentration in Sea Water, Mole Concentration of Dissolved Inorganic Carbon in Sea Water, Bicarbonate Ion Concentration in Sea Water, Sea Ice Concentration, Aragonite Saturation State, Calcite Saturation State, Surface Ocean pH on the Total

Scale, Revelle Factor, Surface dfCO₂ Predicted with a Two-Step Cluster-Regression Approach, Surface Ocean pCO₂, Total Alkalinity Estimated with an Ensemble of SVR Models (scikit-learn).

Initial format: see Gregor, L. and Gruber, N.: OceanSODA-ETHZ: A global gridded data set of the surface ocean carbonate system for seasonal to decadal studies of ocean acidification, Earth Syst. Sci. Data Discuss., <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-13-777-2021>, 2020.

Treatment applied: regridded to a 1 x 1 degree resolution grid and yearly averaged into a monthly climatology.

WOA 2018: <https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/access/world-ocean-atlas-2018/>

Variables : t Temperature (°C) s Salinity (unitless) M Mixed Layer Depth (m) o Dissolved Oxygen (μmol/kg) O Percent Oxygen Saturation (%) A Apparent Oxygen Utilization (μmol/kg) i Silicate (μmol/kg) p Phosphate (μmol/kg) n Nitrate (μmol/kg)

Initial format : see link above

Treatment applied : integrated over depth layers (0-200 m, 0-10m and 200-300 m)

Spatiotemporal resolution

Each dataset has been regridded to the maximal resolution that constitutes a common denominator across all datasets considered. This means, all data products used in the pipeline are regridded to a resolution of 1 degree by 1 degree, monthly climatology, for the surface ocean (top 10 m).

Data formats

All predictor datasets were collected as netcdf files, with most datasets following CF conventions. Where data was provided in another spatiotemporal resolution than the one above, data was regridded to suit the targeted spatiotemporal resolution (see above).

3.2.3. Data annotation of genetic resources from the European Nucleotide Archive

Environmental tags were developed to provide evidence about the likely environments from which data originated, and allow the users and infrastructures such as the Blue-Cloud2026 to explore and retrieve environment-specific records. Two sets of evidence are currently available based on quality-controlled, validated sample attributes: taxonomy and geolocation. Taxonomy-based evidence is obtained from the World Register of Marine Species ([WoRMS](#)) whose taxonomic experts indicate in which of the following environments each taxon is known to occur or not: “marine”, “freshwater” and “terrestrial”. Taxonomy-based evidence also includes a list of “metagenome” taxa from NCBI taxonomy which was manually curated by ENA and associated to the same three environments. Geolocation-based evidence is obtained

from published geospatial data (shapefiles) that set geographic boundaries for the following environments: “marine”, “freshwater” and “terrestrial”. A third set of evidence is under development. It will be based on free-text, non-validated sample attributes that will be parsed against terms of the Environmental Ontology (ENVO) that relate to the “marine”, “freshwater” and “terrestrial” environments.

Biosample: SAMN06266124 [↗](#)

Marine viral communities from the Global Malaspina Expedition - Malaspina viral metaG Antartct_66

Organism:	marine metagenome
Sample Title:	Marine viral communities from the Global Malaspina Expedition - Malaspina viral metaG Antartct_66
Location:	64.45 S 64.88 W
Center Name:	DOE Joint Genome Institute
Sample Alias:	SAMN06266124
Broker Name:	NCBI
Sample Accession:	SAMN06266124
Collection Date:	2015-02-03
Secondary Accession:	SRS2139196
Host:	not applicable
Geo Loc Name:	Antarctica:West Anvers Island
GOLD Ecosystem Classification:	Environmental Aquatic Marine Oceanic Unclassified
Lat Lon:	64.45 S 64.88 W
Isolation Source:	West Anvers Island, Antarctica
Bio Sample Model:	Metagenome or environmental
ENA-FIRST-PUBLIC:	2017-01-25
ENA-LAST-UPDATE:	2022-10-21

Show Less

View: XML

Download: XML

Navigation: Show

Read Files: Show

Analysis Files: Show

3rd Party Curations: Show

ORCID Data Claims: Show

Related ENA Records: Show

Plan Satellite

Google Maps | Données cartographiques | Conditions d'utilisation

Tags

- ▼ environment by taxonomy
 - marine
- ▼ environment by geolocation
 - marine

Figure 5 - Screenshot of the ENA browser that displays the two sets of environmental tags (below the map) for a sample that was collected in the marine environment.

The two sets of evidence (“environment by taxonomy” and “environment by geolocation”) and their tags “marine”, “freshwater” and “terrestrial” are displayed on the ENA browser (figure 3) and are actionable in order to browse through all records that share a given tag. Users can also build their own queries in ENA advanced search based on the environmental tags. In addition, ENA provides Blue-Cloud2026 with predefined queries (curl or https) that return for example a list of records that originate from the marine environment with high, medium or low confidence levels. These confidence levels are obtained by combining tags from the two sets of evidence (Figure 6). Overall, >2 million records from the marine environment are available with medium and high confidence levels (Figure 7).

Figure 6 - Diagram showing how tags from geolocation- and taxonomy-based evidence are used to assess if an ENA record likely originated from the marine environment with (H)igh, (M)edium or (L)ow confidence levels. (!) Cases where the two sets of evidence disagree are used in order to investigate possible mistakes in the metadata. (X) Cases where there is no evidence that the record originated from the marine environment.

Figure 7 - Diagram showing the number of ENA records likely originating from the marine environment with (H)igh, (M)edium or (L)ow confidence levels.

3.2.4. New biological data products using molecular information

The major focus of EMBL-MGnify's work towards this deliverable was to ensure that the various existing and new MGnify data products are suitable for ingestion into the EOv workbench for ecosystem modelling. In work undertaken as part of the AtlantECO project [grant agreement 862923], MGnify has developed an updated version (v6.0) of the MGnify [amplicon analysis pipeline](#). A significant addition to this new version is that it will generate Amplicon Sequence Variant (ASVs) data. This greatly enhances the value of the data that will be extracted from metabarcoding datasets processed by MGnify. The data will contain occurrences and abundances of taxonomically annotated ASVs that can be mapped to sample geolocation metadata as part of this workbench. Once released into production, these new data will supplement the already-expansive collection of amplicon analyses available at the MGnify resource (as well as via GBIF), which now number close to half a million, of which 87,000 are from marine samples. A further significant enhancement to this new version of the amplicon pipeline that was undertaken as part of the DTO-Bioflow project [grant agreement 101112823] is the addition of [PR2](#) as an additional reference database. This vastly improves the coverage of eukaryotic taxonomic annotation that can be applied in analyses, which is of particular importance within Blue-Cloud 2026.

Building on these new data products afforded by v6.0 of the MGnify amplicon pipeline, MGnify have collaborated with colleagues at ETHZ to ensure the format and content of the data outputs are optimal for ingestion into workbench tools such as CEPHALOPOD. Through discussion with the CEPHALOPOD developers it was identified that an additional output file would substantially reduce the overhead of pulling this data into the tool. In response, MGnify have developed a process to generate the required output for some test datasets, allowing the incorporation of MGnify v6.0 results into the workbench to be tested. When testing is complete this additional data product will be included into the new version of the MGnify pipeline, which is expected to be released into production in Q1 of 2025, streamlining the incorporation of new MGnify data into the workbench. Further improvements to the accessibility of these new data will be enacted, including extensions to the MGnify API, to facilitate large-scale data ingestion into this workbench, and therefore, into the Blue-Cloud. This work will be complemented by efforts to define a more expansive mechanism for increasing flow of MGnify data into the Blue-Cloud; this will include mOTUs-based occurrence data that are generated by another independently developed pipeline, which will also soon move into MGnify production.

Another potential route to occurrence data within metagenomic datasets builds on the availability of MGnify Genomes Catalogues. The [MGnify Genomes Marine catalogue v2.0](#) was released in May 2024 as part of work undertaken within the BlueRemediomics project [grant agreement 101082304]. This new version of the marine catalogue contains 50,866 genomes, including both Metagenome Assembled Genomes (MAGs) and isolates, grouped under 13,223 different cluster representatives complete with taxonomic and functional annotation, as well as geographical provenance. This collection of identified

marine genomes functions as a reference set enabling queries such as comparison of MAGs derived from further samples (for example from metagenomic datasets in Blue-Cloud 2026) against the catalogue to determine novelty. It is also possible to use fast kmer-based searches to compare (unassembled) metagenomic datasets against the catalogue with a view to identifying occurrences of catalogue genomes within those datasets. The mechanism to facilitate such queries is currently being prototyped within MGnify with a view to providing further routes to observations data.

All processed biodiversity and biogeographic occurrence information is currently accessible to the project via the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF; www.gbif.org) as presence-only data, for those taxa with an equivalent taxonomic annotation within the World Register of Marine Species (WORMS), comprising a range of prokaryotic and eukaryotic taxa to the highest known taxonomic level, i.e. the species, family, order and/or class level, see link to all existing 23,785,374 occurrences:

<https://www.gbif.org/publisher/ab733144-7043-4e88-bd4f-fca7bf858880>

3.2.5. New biological data products using imaging data

The data released here consist of average species transparency expressed as grey level (0 for dark to 255 for clear). It encompasses 157 Tara Oceans (2009-2012) and 49 Tara Polar Circle (2013) sampling events. All samples had good quality control results on jar tightness and sample preservation, and we removed all non-living parts from the dataset (e.g.: detritus, part, head, etc). 115 taxonomic species or genus were recorded across all stations. The average for each species was calculated as a weighted mean of the individuals' median grey level, the weight being a density factor composed of the fractionation performed for the ZooScan imaging divided by the volume sampled by the net tow. Alongside the transparency the total density factor per species is included so that the community average transparency can be reconstructed if needed, the standard deviation of the weighted average transparency, and the number of individuals to provide robustness information on the value. The UniEuk taxonomic assignments validated by taxonomists were also matched to WoRMS scientific names to ensure consistency with other datasets.

The CSV file (Blue-Cloud2026WB3_D3.1_EBV_Species_Transparency_from_ECOTAXA.csv) and associated README file are available in the WB3_D3.1 folder of the D3.1: <https://data.d4science.net/gZi8>.

3.2.6. Environmental predictor data

CEPHALOPOD accesses a collection of observation-based monthly climatologies of environmental predictors (Fig. 4) that were interpolated on a common grid (i.e., 1 x 1 degree resolution, global scale, gap-filled). We consider monthly surface (0-50 m) or mesopelagic (200-300 m) climatologies encompassing the 1900-2020 period (33 out of 50 climatologies are post 1982). These climatologies are derived from *in-situ* measurements and satellite observations that are commonly used to characterise the physical (e.g.,

sea surface temperature), chemical (e.g., pH) and biological (e.g., Chlorophyll-a concentration) conditions of water masses as well as their circulation and turbulence patterns (e.g., Eddy Kinetic Energy; EKE). A full description of these climatologies is available <https://data.up.ethz.ch/doku.php?id=biocean:readme> and will be published along with the pipeline (Schickele et al. 2024). At this stage, the collection of environmental predictors is available at: <https://data.d4science.net/m9WC>.

Figure 8 - Environmental predictor collection and standardisation for CEPHALOPOD

3.2.7. Preliminary output products as part of D3.1

The local prototype of the workbench’s modelling pipeline (Task 3.4, ETHZ, SU) has been used to generate an initial harmonised set of EOvs (e.g., Fig. 7) and EBVs (e.g., Fig. 8) from presence and biomass data of plankton obtained through traditional microscopy observations. The resulting products are detailed in Tables 12 (EOvs) and 13 (EBVs).

All EOvs and EBVs are 1x1° resolution monthly climatologies delivered in an NetCDF format. All the NetCDF files and associated ReadME files are available in the WB3_D3.1 folder of the D3.1: <https://data.d4science.net/gzi8>.

EOV name	Unit	Resolution	Source data type	Data source	File name
Foraminifera carbon biomass distribution	mg m-3	180° x 360° x 12 months	Abundances converted into carbon biomasses	AtlantECO-v2 (Vogt et al. 2023)	Blue-Cloud2026WB3_D3.1_EOV_Foraminifera_carbon_biomass_interpolated_from_ATLANTECO-BASE1.nc
Pteropoda carbon	mg m-3	180° x 360° x 12 months	Abundances converted into	AtlantECO-v2 (Vogt et al. 2023)	Blue-Cloud2026WB3_D3.1_EOV_Pterop

biomass distribution			carbon biomasses		oda_carbon_biomass_interpolated_from_ATLANTECO-BASE1.nc
Total mesozooplankton carbon biomass distribution	mg m-3	180° x 360° x 12 months	Multiple biomass measurements standardised to carbon biomasses	MAREDAT (Moriarty et al. 2013)	Blue-Cloud2026WB3_D3.1_EOV_Mesozooplankton_carbon_biomass_interpolated_from_MAREDAT.nc

Table 12– List of EOVS delivered by WB3 in D3.1

EBV name	Units	Resolution	Source data type	Data source	File name
Phytoplankton diversity metrics	Number of species	180° x 360° x 12 months x 4 hill scaling factors	Presence only	PHYTOBASE (Vogt et al. 2023)	Blue-Cloud2026WB3_D3.1_EBV_Phytoplankton_Diversity_Metrics_from_PHYTOBASE.nc
Zooplankton diversity metrics	Number of species	180° x 360° x 12 months x 4 hill scaling factors	Presence only	ZOOBASE (Vogt et al. 2023)	Blue-Cloud2026WB3_D3.1_EBV_Zooplankton_Diversity_Metrics_from_ZOOBASE.nc
Total plankton diversity metrics	Number of species	180° x 360° x 12 months x 4 hill scaling factors	Presence only	PHYTOBASE and ZOOBASE (Vogt et al. 2023)	Blue-Cloud2026WB3_D3.1_EBV_Totalplankton_Diversity_Metrics_from_PHYTOBASE_ZOOBASE.nc

Table 13 – List of EBVs delivered by WB3 in D3.1

An example EOVS is visualised in Figure 7 below. It shows (a) a map of total mesozooplankton carbon biomass, based on an extrapolation of existing MAREDAT data (Moriarty et al. 2013) using the CEPHALOPOD pipeline (see section 4.3 below), and (b) the zonal mean of the species distribution model

ensemble, as well as (c) the projections of each individual machine learning models used to compute the machine learning ensemble mean.

Figure 9 – Example EOVS : Extrapolation total mesozooplankton carbon biomass from MAREDAT (Moriarty et al., 20213). (a) Spatial distribution (b) Model ensemble, and (c) individual algorithm latitudinal biomass profiles.

An example EBV is shown in Figure 8 below. Using the new modelling pipeline (see section 4.3 below), global surface ocean zooplankton species richness (alpha diversity) are derived for zooplankton species recorded in the recent ZOOBASE database (Benedetti et al. 2021). Results are shown for different Hill scaling factors: the higher the scaling factor is, lower the weight of the rare biosphere is in the resulting diversity estimate. For instance, a Hill scaling factor of 0 or 1 corresponds to species richness or Shannon diversity estimates, respectively. It is expressed as a number of species (Roswell et al. 2021).

Figure 10 – Example EBV: Total zooplankton diversity from ZOOBASE (Benedetti et al., 2021). The diversity is represented as the number of species according to different Hill scaling factors. The dashed grey areas represent regions of important uncertainty in the projections.

The new and versatile modelling pipeline is currently being tested in a range of scientific applications by colleagues in sister EU projects AtlantECO and BiOceans5D, as well as by the project team and its international collaborators. It is unique in its flexibility, due to the fact that a multitude of biological data types can be taken into account (binary, continuous and proportion data). Ongoing enhancements to the pipeline are set to expand the initial WB3 EOJ and EBV database for D3.2. This includes products derived from biovolume and trait data from imaging, and proportion and compositional biodiversity metrics from new 'omics data.

3.3. Beacon

Partner MARIS, since summer 2021, has been developing the **Beacon software system** with a unique indexing system that can, on the fly, extract specific data based on the user's request from millions of observational data files containing multiple parameters in diverse units. The Beacon system and its data can be accessed via a REST API that is exposed by Beacon itself meaning clients can query data via a simple JSON request, which could be integrated in Jupyter notebooks. The system is built in a way that it returns one single harmonised file as output, regardless of whether the input contains many different data types or dimensions. In practice, Beacon can function as a **data lake** bringing together millions of e.g. NetCDF files from multiple repositories, and after initial indexing (taking several hours), allowing extraction of subsets and exporting these in one coherent NetCDF file in seconds.

After consideration and positive tests on some BDI data collections, it was decided at the latest Blue-Cloud STC meeting, 5-6 March 2024 to embrace the **Beacon** technology for deploying data lakes for Blue-Cloud 2026, both for VRE users as well as for arranging data provision for WorkBenches. This applies in particular for WorkBench 1 (T&S) and WorkBench 2 (Eutrophication).

As a result of the discussions between WP2 and WP3 WorkBench teams and the overall discussions at the STC meeting, two main use cases have been formulated.

- A number of monolithic Beacon instances, each for selected data from a specific BDI, and made available for all Blue-Cloud VRE users;
- Two integrated Beacon instances for WB 1 respectively WB 2, merging and harmonising selected data from multiple BDIs, and with regular and controlled updating mechanism, in connection with the DD&AS, and made available to the 2 WorkBenches.

The planned set-up of these use cases is described in more detail in (Schaap 2024). Since the STC meeting and delivery of the document great progress has been made towards adding functionality to the Beacon system and towards establishing the two planned configurations.

3.3.1. Beacon updates

As Beacon¹ needs to enable subsetting across a wide range of BDI's with each BDI having millions of datasets, some of the internal structures within Beacon had to be optimised:

- Memory usage of indexes that Beacon uses to find the datasets that contain data relevant to the query made by the client was optimised. The initial index implementation was sufficient enough when working with 3 to 4 millions files, however, some BDI's contained up to 25 million datasets, which caused an increase in memory and slowed down performance significantly. To address this, the index had its basic memory layout adjusted to make it more memory efficient and "lock-free", meaning multiple cores of the system could safely simultaneously traverse the index;
- Support for querying on variable attributes (metadata of the data) was enabled by improvements on how Beacon internally handles metadata (attributes) of columns. This update resulted in the following changes:
 - A user can now, for example, add the SeaDataNet instrument that was used for the temperature column as an additional output column;
 - This also enabled Beacon to have an easier time when exporting to ODV as one can simply add more metadata columns in the query which can then be simply appended as additional columns in the ODV output;
 - This update also includes range filtering as we previously only supported exact match filtering on attributes. Eg. instead of "platform_number" = 5, one can now do: "platform_number" >= 5. This applies to all column types, so range filtering on text is also supported.
- Beacon can now support queries larger than memory if enabled when starting up a Beacon instance. This can be helpful when querying multi-year exports;
- Enable the use of functions in queries which is a starting point for on-the-fly cross BDI query harmonisation. E.g. translate "julian days since 1770" to "julian days since 1950";
- Speed up the import of ODV products, there was also another import driver developed specifically for importing webODV ASCII. This driver is significantly faster as the NetCDF output of ODV uses "sparse" data columns which makes it inefficient and slow to import the entire collection into Beacon. This would also enable an easier integration into the proposed data pipeline by which ODV re-exports its validated data to another Beacon instance for subsetting.

¹ For more information see <https://beacon.maris.nl/> & <https://maris-development.github.io/beacon/>.

- Using the Beacon instances requires user registration and user transactions are logged in an administration dashboard at MARIS so that later BDI operators can retrieve KPI information about the use of their data resources via Beacon queries.

As many of the BDI's provided millions of datasets each, an efficient way of importing was required. This was achieved by writing Rust/C native import drivers that were directly embedded into the Beacon Source code allowing the reading of the datasets. This approach was followed, since the performance of using a Python script to transform the datasets into individual profiles was not good enough. In the sections below, the drivers for the Physics and Eutrophication Workbenches are listed.

3.3.2. Beacon Physics WorkBench

The following drivers were created for the Physics WorkBench (WB1):

- WOD import driver (shared instance with the Eutrophication WB)
- CORA-PR import driver
- ARGO import driver
- WebODV import driver (SeaDataNet CDI T&S collection)
- SeaDataNet CDI service import driver (SeaDataNet CDI T&S data sets since mid 2019)

The following Physics WB BDI sources use the original NetCDFimport driver as they did not have the issue of sparse data described in Deliverable 2.4.

- CORA-TS import driver

3.3.3. Beacon Eutrophication WorkBench

The following drivers were created for the Eutrophication WorkBench (WB2):

- CMEMS BGC PR import driver (only the profiles files, they are still imported into the same CMEMS BGC instance as the timeseries files)
- WOD import driver (shared instance with the Physics WB)
- WebODV import driver (Emodnet Chemistry North Atlantic)

The following Eutrophication WB BDI sources use the original NetCDF import driver as they did not have the issue of sparse data described in Deliverable 2.4.

- CMEMS BGC import driver (only the time series files, they are still imported into the same CMEMS BGC instance as the profiles files)

3.3.4. Beacon demonstration notebooks

There are currently eight demonstrator notebooks available on [GitHub](#) and the Blue-Cloud [VRE](#) connected to the following Beacon instances:

- [beacon-argo.maris.nl](#)
 - Euro-Argo data, retrieved from [S3 bucket](#)
- [beacon-cora-pr.maris.nl](#)
 - CORA Profile data, retrieved from CMEMS, product:
[INSITU_GLO_PHY_TS_DISCRETE_MY_013_001](#)
- [beacon-cora-ts.maris.nl](#)
 - CORA Timeseries data, retrieved from CMEMS, product:
[INSITU_GLO_PHY_TS_DISCRETE_MY_013_001](#)
- [beacon-emod-chem.maris.nl](#)
 - EMODnet Chemistry data, retrieved from [EMODnet Chemistry WebODV \(Eutrophication Atlantic profiles 2023 unrestricted.odv\)](#)
- [beacon-wod.maris.nl](#)
 - WOD data, retrieved from [ncei.noaa.gov](#)
- [beacon-cmems.maris.nl](#)
 - CMEMS BGC data, retrieved from CMEMS, product:
[INSITU_GLO_BGC_DISCRETE_MY_013_046](#)
- [beacon-cdi-ts.maris.nl](#)
 - SeaDataNet CDI TS data, retrieved from [EGI-ACE webODV](#)
- [beacon-cdi-incremental.maris.nl/](#)
 - SeaDataNet CDI TS data extract between 2019 and 2024

The Figure 9 below illustrates a part of the demonstrator notebook for the World Ocean Database (WOD) Beacon instance. In order to run the Notebook, the user first needs to get a unique access token. With this token, they can then send a post request to the specific Beacon instance endpoint and retrieve the data corresponding to their query. Here it is then visualised on a map, and users can apply further post-processing methods, if required.

This is the post request that is sent to Beacon with the above specified body.

```
In [8]: response = requests.post("https://beacon-wod.maris.nl/api/query", json.dumps(query), headers = {
    'Authorization': f'Bearer {Token}',
    'Content-type': 'application/json'
})

if response.status_code == 204:
    print('No data has been found for your query, please update your input fields above and run the notebook again.')
elif response.status_code != 200:
    print(response.text)
```

This will create a Netcdf file in your directory with the name based on your filters, the output is shown here in a dataframe.

```
In [9]: open(f'WOD_{parameter}_{regionname}_{mintemp.strftime("%Y-%m-%d")}-{maxtemp.strftime("%Y-%m-%d")}_{mindepth}-{maxdepth}.nc', 'w')
df = xr.open_dataset(f'WOD_{parameter}_{regionname}_{mintemp.strftime("%Y-%m-%d")}-{maxtemp.strftime("%Y-%m-%d")}_{mindepth}-{maxdepth}.nc')
```

Out[9]:

	Temperature	TIME	DEPTH	LONGITUDE	LATITUDE	DATASET	cruise-identifier	cast	WMO_ID	country	dataset_id
INSTANCE											
0	17.889999	84148.386111	0.000000	-9.498100	37.139999	drifting buoy	US016567	9239821	62763	UNITED STATES	8464989
1	17.719999	84148.386111	3.000000	-9.498100	37.139999	drifting buoy	US016567	9239821	62763	UNITED STATES	8464989
2	17.639999	84148.386111	8.000000	-9.498100	37.139999	drifting buoy	US016567	9239821	62763	UNITED STATES	8464989
3	17.639999	84148.386111	10.000000	-9.498100	37.139999	drifting buoy	US016567	9239821	62763	UNITED STATES	8464989
4	25.370001	84089.000000	1.000000	-155.029999	0.000000	moored buoy	US015907	9135992	51023	UNITED STATES	8491211
...
773704	3.759000	84066.277778	8.000000	137.501389	37.186943	CTD	JP037213	13613604	0	JAPAN	8435327
773705	3.759000	84066.277778	9.000000	137.501389	37.186943	CTD	JP037213	13613604	0	JAPAN	8435327
773706	3.759000	84066.277778	10.000000	137.501389	37.186943	CTD	JP037213	13613604	0	JAPAN	8435327
773707	16.810100	84224.022310	7.042896	-125.089981	43.999821	towed CTD	US016986	10035632	0	UNITED STATES	8560160
773708	16.558701	84224.022310	9.423538	-125.089981	43.999821	towed CTD	US016986	10035632	0	UNITED STATES	8560160

773709 rows x 11 columns

Plotting of results, if there are a lot of measurements, it may take quite some time (+5 min).

```
In [10]: import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from mpl_toolkits.basemap import Basemap
from mpl_toolkits.axes_grid1 import make_axes_locatable
fig = plt.figure(1, figsize = (29, 19))

m = Basemap(projection = 'cyl', llcrnrlon = minlon, llcrnrlat = minlat, urcrnrlon = maxlon, urcrnrlat = maxlat, resolution = 'c')
m.drawlsmask(land_color = 'Linen', ocean_color = '#CCFFFF'); # can use HTML names or codes for colors
m.drawcoastlines()
m.drawcountries()

sc = m.scatter(df['LONGITUDE'], df['LATITUDE'], latlon = True, c = df[parameter], cmap = plt.cm.jet)

plt.title(f'WOD {parameter} {regionname} {mintemp.strftime("%Y-%m-%d")}-{maxtemp.strftime("%Y-%m-%d")} [{mindepth}-{maxdepth}] #')
ax = plt.gca()
divider = make_axes_locatable(ax)
cax = divider.append_axes("right", size = "5%", pad = 0.05)
plt.colorbar(sc, cax = cax, label = f'{parameter} {unit}');
```


Figure 11 – World Ocean Database (WOD) demonstration notebook. This Figure shows the last few cells of the notebook, where data is being retrieved from the corresponding WOD beacon endpoint. Here you can see temperature measurements for the year 2000, for the top 10 metres of the ocean at a global scale, resulting in more than 700,000 measurements

3.3.5. Next steps for Beacon

Further optimise Beacon

The index, while it's sufficient in its current state, should be optimised further to reduce the pressure on the memory available by a server. This in turns allows queries to also make more efficient use of the memory available that was previously used by the index.

Deployment at Blue-Cloud VRE

The 8 Beacon instances and notebooks are currently deployed and operational at the MARIS e-infrastructure and available for controlled use by WorkBench colleagues, who need to contact MARIS for registration. Developments are well underway between MARIS and CNR for parallel deployment of these 8 Beacon instances and notebooks at the D4Science e-infrastructure as part of the Blue-Cloud VRE, giving access to all users registered as Blue-Cloud users. The VRE deployment will also connect to the KPI dashboard that MARIS is managing for tracking use of the Beacon instances and for sharing KPIs with operators of the BDIs whose data resources are made accessible via Beacon.

Combining output from multiple monolithic Beacon instances into integrated Beacon instances for WBs

A start has been made with setting up two integrated Beacon instances for supporting WB1 and WB2. This will be done using a pyramid approach, federating query output from monolithic Beacon instances, relevant for WB1 respectively WB2, into two integrated Beacon instances. A structural mapping analysis will be performed for each monolithic Beacon versus the target Common Metadata Profile as defined by the WB teams (see §2.1), including triplets for object name, object code, and object vocabulary. These mappings will be used in the Beacon queries to retrieve and load contents 'as-is' from monolithic Beacon instances into the two integrated Beacon instances, giving a common structure for variables, units, values, quality flags, and common metadata profile fields. The structured metadata and data will be supplemented by additional metadata data as available for each of the monolithic Beacon instances.

This first step will allow footprints of contents for each of the fields from the Common Metadata Profile, including possible vocabularies in use, which will be shared with partner NOC-BODC for their semantic analyses. These footprints will be trimmed by focusing on the variables which are priority for each of the two WBs.

Harmonising the Contents of the Common Metadata Profile fields, parameters and units

As a second step, use will be made of data conversions rules and semantic mappings to be provided as services by partner NOC-BODC for harmonising the contents of the fields for parameters, units, and Common Metadata Profile fields as loaded into each of the two integrated Beacon instances. This will be done on-the-fly as part of Beacon queries and should result in homogeneous outputs for the data and common metadata, supplemented with additional metadata as available. The homogeneous output can

then be loaded into WebODV using the already proven machine-to-machine exchange. The NOC-BODC mappings will increase gradually which will contribute to gradual increase of the homogenisation of the Beacon output.

Remarks: The Beacon process will leave quality analysis and seeking duplicates to WebODV and the WB experts.

Dashboard for regulating and administering harvests:

The WBs, once in production, will work with production cycles. For instance, each 6 or 12 months, an updated version of an EOV data collection could be generated, adding the new and updated data from the last period to the existing and already validated EOV data collection product. This implies that the WorkBench teams would prefer to keep control of new and updated data harvests that will reach WebODV via queries on the integrated Beacon instances. That way, WB experts could focus on only the incremental metadata and data sets, while not having to process again the data sets that were already validated in the previous run. Therefore, partner MARIS will develop a dashboard for use by WB operators which will keep track of the DD&AS pipeline from BDIs to monolithic Beacon instances to integrated Beacon instances to WebODV ingestions.

More notebooks

Once new Beacon instances are installed, accompanying notebooks will be created. Using Slack, the feedback and user experience from previous notebooks will be taken into account, to improve existing ones.

Generic Beacon WMS interface

Great progress is being made by partner MARIS with a generic Beacon WMS interface, in which the user is easily able to select filters for time, area, depth, parameter and visualise the data on a map. A further step would be to allow for downloading of the data via the interface.

3.4. Integrating Beacon output into webODV

Beacon allows the output dataset to be exported in different formats including a .txt version compatible with ODV, which at the moment is limited to the desktop version of the software. The integration of beacon output into webODV with other formats is still under development in collaboration with developers of partners AWI and MARIS.

Figure 10 shows the BEACON output loaded into webODV in D4Science. The dataset was obtained by querying the EMODnet chemistry BEACON instance in the DD&AS using the query in Appendix 1. Then the

.txt output was loaded to the ODV desktop version and converted to an odv collection since currently this is the only format allowed in the D4science version of webODV.

Figure 12 - Integration of Beacon output into webODV in D4science.

4. Workbenches workflow

4.1. Physical WorkBench

4.1.1. Schematic overview

Figure 11 displays a schematic overview of the WB1 design which shows its dependency from Beacon to retrieve a homogenised dataset which integrates data coming from four main Temperature and Salinity

(T&S) data repositories and data collections: Copernicus Marine Service (CMEMS), SeaDataNet (SDN), EuroArgo and World Ocean Database (WOD). Specific queries to Beacon will be run by the WB experts through Jupyter Notebooks in the first phase but a dashboard development is planned by Beacon’s developers that will be used when ready. A first feedback loop is established with the BDIs managers of the interesting input datasets in order to continuously improve their data access services and semantic interoperability, which is key for rapid and efficient big data consumption on a VRE.

Figure 13– Schematic overview of Physical WorkBench

The Beacon output can be loaded in webODV service, operating on the VRE, for data exploration, visualisation and further analysis. webODV service could be used to obtain the final added value T&S dataset since it allows duplicate removal functionality and additional Quality Control (QC) capabilities, however this approach is advisable only for regional and sub-regional studies since it requires human intervention, which might be huge for global studies. A complementary automatic workflow will be implemented through the deployment of specific softwares for duplicate detection (CloneWars tool) and handling an additional QC (MinMax tool) on the physical WB VLab, specifically set up by the WP5 team considering the WB technical requirements. Additional feedback loops will be implemented to report back to the source BDIs the detected duplicates, the data and metadata anomalies. To this purpose the preservation of data provenance is essential to be able to track back the data in the source BDIs. Additional tools, developed by the IQuoD group (<https://www.iquod.org/>, Simoncelli et al., 2024), for duplicate management (DC_OCEAN, [Song et al. 2024](#)) and additional QC (Tan et al., 2023) have been identified

during the Literature Survey and they might be adapted and deployed on the VRE, once the previously described workflow is in operation. This activity aims at maintaining a collaboration with international experts, working on data management and QC.

Validation of the final harmonised EOv dataset for the Mediterranean Sea will be performed:

- visually using webODV and following the methodology first applied in SeaDataCloud project;
- using the DIVAnd tool to derive climatologies from the single input data sets and the final BC EOv dataset.

The mapping package first prepared within the SeaDataCloud project (Simoncelli et al., 2021) and based on DIVAnd tool (<https://github.com/gher-uliege/DIVAnd.jl>), will be adapted and deployed on the VRE to prove the added value of the physical WB output dataset with respect to the initial inputs, through the production of gridded climatologies for the Mediterranean Sea as derived product.

The first workflow implementation will focus on the Mediterranean basin and, once in operation, it will be tested at global scale.

4.1.2. Physical WB workflow components on the Blue Cloud VRE

The automatic workflow implementation is based on the deployment of specific softwares for duplicate detection (CloneWars tool) and handling an additional QC (MinMax tool) on the WB1 VLab. The WP5 team set up the WB1 VLab environment considering the technical requirements for the implementation of these 2 tools developed by the team of partner POKaPOK .

CloneWars

Clone Wars tool is designed to look for duplicates in datasets. Through a specific graphical user interface, the user can :

- select the datasets to work with. Data can come from different sources (e.g.: EMODnet, Copernicus Marine Service) or not. The user can choose a specific geographical area, a time frame, some parameters and/or instruments of interest, etc;
- choose between various “duplicate definitions” by parametrizing several criteria: what are the allowed time and space differences? Should one use the instrument type as an additional criterion or not? Should one look for duplicates inside a given data source or only between different data sources? etc.;
- launch the duplicate search;
- analyse the results. Clone Wars produces a set of figures in order to locate the potential duplicates on a world map, and to display statistics on the available number of depth levels, the available parameters and their global quality (by analysing the QC flag values). To go into a more detailed

analysis, potential duplicates can also be grouped either by platform code or by cruise name (depending on what was available in the initial dataset) and the display will be updated accordingly.

As Clone Wars relies on a set of R functions, once the initial dataset and the duplicate definition for Blue Cloud operations will be available, then the tool will slightly evolve to allow also a fully automated use (without the user-interface).

Overview : Simplified workflow

- Harvest user's requirements in terms of data selection and duplicate's definition
- Display duplicate's analysis results with different levels of details
- Collect the user's decision regarding duplicates (which one to keep ? which one to reject ?)

Figure 14 – CloneWars workflow (from presentation at <https://data.d4science.net/m8QL>)

MinMax

The principle of the MinMax test is relatively simple: the test checks whether new incoming data fall inside or outside a given validity interval. Data inside the validity interval are considered as correct whereas data falling outside the validity interval will raise an alert and will be sent to an operator for further inspection.

In the 1D version, each parameter is checked independently and validity intervals are defined through Minimum and Maximum acceptable values for each parameter. Extrema values are provided all over the world and for several depth layers from the surface and down to 5500 m depth.

Minimum and maximum values come from existing datasets and the initial interval is then widened in order to account for the unsampled natural variability, to optimise the number of good and false alarms, and to fit operational constraints (i.e. to produce a reasonable number of daily alerts that is manageable by an operator).

In the 2D version, two parameters are checked simultaneously and thus the validity interval evolves into a validity area (defined using a polygon). But the test principle and the need for widening remains the same.

4.2. Eutrophication workbench

4.2.1. Schematic overview and tools available on the Blue-Cloud VRE

Figure 13 depicts in detail the elements of the Eutrophication WB workflow. As it can be seen, the dependency with Beacon and thus with the SA is quite high.

Figure 15 - Eutrophication workbench workflow

As stated before, the WB2 aims to generate harmonised and validated EOv data collections for Chl, nutrients and oxygen (Table 14 shows in detail the P02 codes and the description from the selected EOvs²) integrating datasets from different BDIs. In this case from WOD, EMODnet-chemistry and CMEMS.

P02	Description
CPWC	Chlorophyll pigment concentrations in water bodies
DOXY	Dissolved oxygen parameters in the water column
TEMP	Temperature of the water column
PSAL	Salinity of the water column

² Note that P02 and P09 use the same terms with different meanings.

TDPX	Dissolved total or organic phosphorus concentration in the water column
TPHS	Particulate total and organic phosphorus concentrations in the water column
PHOS	Phosphate concentration parameters in the water column
TDIN	Dissolved inorganic nitrogen concentration in the water column
NTRA	Nitrate concentration parameters in the water column
NTRI	Nitrite concentration parameters in the water column
AMON	Ammonium and ammonia concentration parameters in water bodies
SLCA	Silicate concentration parameters in the water column

Table 14 - selected EOvs, their respective P02 codes and description.

This phase is going to be done using the Beacon API, where thanks to the SA the WB team will obtain the semantic rules to effectively query the API and merge the desired datasets. The output obtained using Beacon will be available in netCDF and ODV formats which in turn will be loaded into webODV for duplicate check (phase two). In this phase, also use will be made of CloneWars, a toolbox written in R and R-shiny developed by POKaPOK, as an additional tool for duplicate detection. CloneWars, as stated before, looks for duplicates inside a range of time and space (not only identical values for time and position), requires at least one common measured parameter to be identified as a potential duplicate, it is able to handle parameters with different measured units and also allows a visual inspection of the results.

Once the datasets will be harmonised and validated for each EOv, gridded fields and climatologies will be computed using the [DIVAnd tool](#) (Barth, A et al., 2014) starting from the North east Atlantic sea (1st release) and with the aim to extend it to the global ocean by the end of the project. This step is also important and connected to WP4, Marine Environmental Indicators VLab, where the data collections will be used to calculate eutrophication indicators in coastal areas.

4.3. Ecosystem workbench

4.3.1. Schematic overview

The WB team developed a new habitat modelling framework called CEPHALOPOD (Comprehensive Ensemble Pipeline for Habitat modelling Across Large-scale Ocean Pelagic Observation Datasets) to derive global scale, gap-filled, harmonised and inter-comparable EOvs and EBVs from near-real time plankton in-situ observation datasets (Fig. 16).

In short, the pipeline first accesses near-real time collections of in-situ plankton observation data from various sources within Blue-Cloud 2026, including OBIS, GBIF, AtlantECO, and MATOU. Those will be extended in the near future to include cutting edge plankton observations derived from quantitative imaging (Ecotaxa) and genomic methods (ASVs and Metagenome Assemble Genomes; via MGnify - EBI;

Fig. 16, step 1-2). These datasets contain plankton occurrences, abundances, biomasses and proportions of metagenomic reads. After selecting the target taxa, it associates the in-situ observations with the environmental conditions at the sample locations, retrieved from the collection of environmental climatologies described above (**Fig. 16, step 3**). Both biological and environmental data undergo a series of pre-processing and quality checks to ensure a parsimonious input dataset, and discard eventual outliers or non-informative predictors. When necessary, biological in-situ observations are matched against a taxonomic reference (WoRMS catalogue) to correct unaccepted or synonym taxonomic annotations. Then, CEPHALOPOD defines hyper-parameters and builds training and testing datasets for each algorithm and taxa considered. It is based on an ensemble modelling approach, meaning that it will always prioritise EOvs and EBVs constructed from several quality checked algorithms. To do so, it selects the best hyperparameters and evaluates the performance of each algorithm using the latest and commonly accepted best practices in the field (**Fig. 16, step 4**). Spatial projections are obtained for each algorithm and taxa successfully passing the quality checks, and combined in EOvs and EBVs (**Fig. 16, step 5**). The final output includes those spatial projections, a comprehensive quality check report and recommendations based on a traffic light system (**Fig. 16, step 6**). The full documentation of CEPHALOPOD is available on [GitHub](#) and will be published along with Schickele et al., submitted.

15Figure 16 - Illustration of the CEPHALOPOD workflow, a standardised habitat modelling pipeline across data types, developed for automatic generation of high-quality EOvs and EBVs from Blue-Cloud 2026 partner biological data repositories (Schickele et al., submitted)

4.3.2. Elements (API) available on the blue Cloud VRE

A fully automated prototype of the pipeline has been successfully ported to the Blue-Cloud2026 cloud computing platform (Fig. 15). It can now run seamlessly on Blue-Cloud, accessing both biological and environmental datasets hosted in the Ecosystem Workbench VRE. Users can initiate the pipeline with a simple click, selecting input and output locations within the VRE. To ensure compatibility, the prototype is packaged in a Docker container with all necessary dependencies. The output includes EOv and EBv

netCDF files, along with traffic light recommendations and maps in PDF format. While the pipeline currently supports up to four species, future improvements will focus on automating input access from online repositories and enhancing computing power for D3.2. For now, high-quality outputs are provided by the local prototype rather than the cloud-based version (see below).

Figure 17 - Screenshot of the first CEPHALOPOD prototype ported on the Blue-Cloud2026 Cloud Computing Platform (CCP)

5. Conclusions

WP3 and the WBs are on track. An important difficulty and strength is that the workbenches need the technical developments of WP2 (e.g. Semantic Analyser, Beacon, Data Lakes) and of WP5 (e.g. VLabs, API available on D4Sciences) to be built.

The main idea of the WBs is to design, build, deploy and test on the Blue-Cloud VRE analytical pipelines for generating highly qualified and harmonised data collections for selected Essential Ocean and Biological Variables (EOV and EBV respectively), whereby the input data sets are derived from multiple and different BDIs.

For the physical and the eutrophication WBs, the harmonised output dataset will be without duplicates and with an added QC from the ones of the input datasets (and done by different experts).

In order to harmonise the input datasets, a mapping of the metadata used in each of them is necessary and is largely described in this document. This is done thanks to the support of partner BODC (working in

WP2) and will be improved till the end of the project through iteration between the WBs and the metadata experts.

For the ecosystem WB, the harmonised output dataset will allow the display and the visualisation of different kinds (microscopy observations, imaging, omics') of data. The first steps of the WB have been built locally to illustrate and test the whole chain before being ported in the D4Sciences VRE and using all different data types.

The construction of the WBs is definitely an iterative process between input and output data to increase the number of data, to upgrade the metadata mapping, to use duplicates techniques, to use other validation tools & process, to be able to visualise different data types ... that has started and will continue till the end of the project and beyond to obtain harmonised datasets that have never been achieved before.

These WB constructions are an important element to use and add value to the BDIs and the Research Infrastructures (RI) by using several of them, comparing them and visualising them. In that sense, and as other parts of developments ensured in Blue Cloud 2026, WBs can be used and proposed as examples and demonstrators of what is possible to do on the future DTO.

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Appendix 1: BEACON query for ODV output

```
def query(parameter, mintemporal, maxtemporal, mindepth, maxdepth,
minlon, maxlon, minlat, maxlat):
    body = {
        "query_parameters": [
            {
                "column_name": "ITS_90_water_temperature",
                "alias": "Temperature [celsius]"
            },
            {
                "column_name": "ITS_90_water_temperature_qc",
                "alias": "Temperature_qc"
            },
            {
                "column_name": "date_time",
                "alias": "TIME"
            },
            {
                "function": "time::const_convert_datetime_to_iso",
                "epoch": "1921-01-01T00:00:00Z",
                "unit": "days",
                "input": {
                    "column_name": "date_time"
                },
                "alias": "IsoTime"
            },
            {
                "column_name": "Depth",
                "alias": "Depth [meter]"
            }
        ]
    }
```

```

    },
    {
      "column_name": "Depth_gc",
      "alias": "Depth_gc"
    },
    {
      "column_name": "longitude",
      "alias": "LONGITUDE"
    },
    {
      "column_name": "latitude",
      "alias": "LATITUDE"
    },
    {
      "column_name": "EDMO_code",
      "alias": "EDMO_code"
    },
  ],
  "filters": [
    {
      "for_query_parameter": "TIME",
      "min": mintemporal,
      "max": maxtemporal
    },
    {
      "for_query_parameter": "Depth [meter]",
      "min": mindepth,
      "max": maxdepth
    },
    {
      "for_query_parameter": "LONGITUDE",
      "min": minlon,
      "max": maxlon
    },
    {
      "for_query_parameter": "LATITUDE",
      "min": minlat,
      "max": maxlat
    }
  ],
  "output": {
    "format": {
      "odv": {
        "longitude_column": "LONGITUDE",
        "latitude_column": "LATITUDE",
        "timestamp_column": {
          "data_column_name": "IsoTime",
          "comment": ""
        }
      }
    }
  }
},

```

```

        "depth_column": {
            "data_column_name": "Depth [meter]",
            "comment": "",
            "qf_column": "Depth_qc"
        },
        "data_columns": [
            {
                "data_column_name": "Temperature
[celsius]",
                "comment": "",
                "qf_column": "Temperature_qc"
            }
        ],
        "metadata_columns": [
            "EDMO_code"
        ],
        "skip_odv_script": False,
        "qf_schema": "SEADATANET"
    }
}
return body

query = query(parameter, mintemporal, maxtemporal, mindepth,
              maxdepth, minlon, maxlon, minlat, maxlat)

print(query)

```